

2nd Meeting of Young Biophysicists

Biophysics Festival 2022

June 3rd | Aveiro

Book of Abstracts

Organization

Portuguese Young Biophysicists
Núcleo de jovens biofísicos

Sponsors

Design

Organizing Committee

André Miranda CICS-UBI, Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior

Arménio Barbosa UCIBIO-i4HB, Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia da Universidade Nova de Lisboa

Catarina Pimpão iMED.Ulisboa, Faculdade de Farmácia da Universidade de Lisboa

Daniela Duarte CICECO - Aveiro Institute of Materials, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro

Inês Silva iMED.Ulisboa, Faculdade de Farmácia da Universidade de Lisboa

Mariana Valério Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica da Universidade Nova de Lisboa

Nelly Silva IMM-JLA, Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Lisboa

Philip O'Toole UCIBIO-i4HB, Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia da Universidade Nova de Lisboa

Rita Ferreira LAQV, REQUIMTE, Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade do Porto

Tatiana João CICECO - Aveiro Institute of Materials, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro

Scientific Committee

Arménio Barbosa UCIBIO-i4HB, Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia da Universidade Nova de Lisboa

Cláudia Rodrigues IMM-JLA, Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Lisboa

Carla Sousa Helmholtz Institute, Saarbrücken, Germany

Catarina Jesus CICECO - Aveiro Institute of Materials, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro

Filipe Coreta-Gomes, LAQV, REQUIMTE, Universidade de Aveiro

Hugo Filipe CPIRN-IPG, Escola Superior de Saúde, Instituto Politécnico da Guarda

Jacinta Pinto iMED.Ulisboa, Faculdade de Farmácia da Universidade de Lisboa

Mariana Ferreira LAQV, REQUIMTE, Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade do Porto

Micael Silva Weizmann Institute of Science, Israel

Tânia Santos Weizmann Institute of Science, Israel

Sponsors and Acknowledgements

Welcome Message From Portuguese Biophysics Society

Fellow Biophysicists,

it is my pleasure to welcome you to the Biophysics Festival 2022. Science thrives on open discussions, a sense of community, collaborative endeavors, and also strong inter-personal bonds. Collaborative and inter-personal links established early in a scientific career not only catalyze the progress of Science, but also remain a major stimulus for personal growth throughout life. But while the major congresses in Biophysics provide good networking opportunities for young researchers, their programs are designed mainly by and for established scientists, which inevitably dilutes the opportunities for younger scientists to present their work and interact.

These considerations led the Portuguese Biophysics Society to kickstart a series of yearly short meetings, designed by and for early-career scientists for the enjoyment of their research and promoting informal socializing. The first such meeting, the Biophysics Party, took place in July 6, 2018 at ITQB-Nova. It was very participated and successful, but after this auspicious start, the COVID-19 pandemic has prevented further meetings for the past two years. Meanwhile, the severe limitations to in-person interactions posed by the public-health situation make presencial meetings like this more important than ever. Therefore, I am very grateful to the Young Portuguese Biophysicists Group to have so enthusiastically organized this *Biophysics Festival*, which I believe will be not only successful, but also a memorable event for a generation of Portuguese biophysicists.

Armindo Salvador

President of the Portuguese Biophysical Society

Welcome Message From The Organizing Committee

Dear attendees,

the organizing committee of the Young Portuguese Biophysicists Group, of the Portuguese Biophysics Society, welcomes you to the 2nd Meeting of Young Biophysicists – “*2022 Biophysics Festival*” – at the University of Aveiro.

This event aims to gather students and young scientists working in Biophysics, and related disciplines, to promote networking and knowledge exchange in a casual environment. We want the Biophysics Festival to be not only a comfortable place to communicate your most recent research, but also an opportunity to meet each other and share your knowledge with experts in the field.

In this one-day event, you will be able to hear from invited speakers and participants working on a wide range of topics related to Biophysics, so we encourage you to bring your questions and reflections.

We would like to express our gratitude to all that contributed to this event, specially to University of Aveiro for welcoming us, to our invited speakers and sponsors, to the Scientific Committee, and to the Portuguese Biophysics Society for all encouragement and support. Last, but not least, we acknowledge all participants for coming and participating in this event and we hope you can enjoy this event with us.

Finally, we believe the Biophysics Festival will provide an inspiring atmosphere for fruitful networking among all participants and promote future collaborations.

Kindest regards,

Young Portuguese Biophysicists Group

Programme

9:00-10:00 – Registration

10:00-10:15 – Opening and Welcome Session

Nuno Santos, Portuguese Biophysics Society

Ana Lillebo Batista, Vice-Rector for Quality, Communication and Efficiency, University of Aveiro

Tatiana Carneiro, Representant of Organizing Committee

Scientific Session 1

Chairperson: Nuno Santos

Oral Communications

10:15-10:30 – TARGETING DENGUE AND ZIKA VIRUS WITH NEW BRAIN- AND PLACENTA-CROSSING PEPTIDE-PORPHYRIN CONJUGATES

Diogo A. Mendonça - *Instituto de Medicina Molecular João Lobo Antunes, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal*

10:30-10:45 – DESIGN, PRODUCTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ANTIVIRAL PROTEINS TARGETING SARS-COV-2

Susana Parreiras - *ITQB NOVA, Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Oeiras, Portugal*

10:45-11:30 – Coffee Break and Poster Session

Scientific Session 2

Chairperson: Paula Gameiro

Oral Communications

11:30-11:45 – G-QUADRUPLEX FORMING MOTIFS IN THE PROMOTER REGION OF THE B-MYB PROTO-ONCOGENE: A TARGET FOR CANCER THERAPY?

André Miranda - *CICS-UBI - Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal*

11:45-12:00 – SYNCHROTRON-BASED INFRARED MICROSPECTROSCOPY OF NANOPLATFORMS AND SKIN: UNVEILING MOLECULAR INTERACTIONS

Ana Isabel Barbosa - *LAQV, REQUIMTE, Departamento de Ciências Químicas, Faculdade de Farmácia, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal*

12:00-14:00 – Lunch - Aveiro University Canteen

Scientific Session 3

Chairperson: Hugo Louro

Plenary Lecture

14:00-14:30 – PROBING THE STRUCTURAL PLASTICITY OF THE POTASSIUM CHANNEL KCSA USING HOMO-FRET METHODOLOGIES

Ana Coutinho, *Professor at Faculty of Sciences of University of Lisbon, and Senior Researcher at iBB in Instituto Superior Técnico*

Oral Communications

14:30-14:45 – POLYSACCHARIDES HYPOCHOLESTEROLEMIC POTENTIAL: FROM STRUCTURE TO FUNCTION

Filipe Coreta-Gomes – *LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal*

14:45-15:00 – FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF AN ELECTRON: BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF CYTOCHROME CBCL AND ITS REDOX COMPLEXES IN EXTRACELLULAR ELECTRON TRANSFER

Jorge M. A. Antunes - *Associate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Almada, Portugal*

Plenary Lecture

15:00-15:30 – UPS AND DOWNS OF HUNTING WHAT TRIGGERS AND DIRECT COLLECTIVE

Elias Barriga, *Instituto Gulbenkian da Ciência (IGC)*

15:30-16:30 – Coffee Break and Poster Session

Scientific Session 4

Chairperson: Manuel Prieto

Flash Communications

16:30-17:00

PHASE-SEPARATING FUSED IN SARCOMA UNDERGOES COLD DENATURATION UPON COLD STRESS

Sara S. Félix - *Associate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Almada, Portugal*

MOLECULAR DETERMINANTS OF THE SARS-COV-2 FUSION PEPTIDE ACTIVITY

Carolina C. Buga - *ITQB NOVA, Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Oeiras, Portugal*

SOLUTION STRUCTURES OF ATAXIN-3 IN COMPLEX WITH NANOBODIES WITH ANTI-AGGREGATION PROPERTIES

Vitor Vieira - *IBMC – Instituto de Biologia Molecular e Celular, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal*

ENGINEERING OF ELECTRON TRANFER PROTEINS TO IMPROVE BIOENERGY PRODUCTION

Alexandre Almeida - *Associate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Almada, Portugal*

Closing Lecture

17:00-17:30 – HIGHLY PACKED PROTEOLIPID MULTILAYERED MEMBRANES TO STABILIZE AND PROTECT THE RESPIRATORY SURFACE

Jesus Perez-Gil, Professor and Dean of Biology at Complutense University of Madrid, and President Spanish Biophysical Society

17:30-17:50 – Closing Remarks and Awards Ceremony

Nuno Santos, Portuguese Biophysics Society

Tatiana João, Representant of Organizing Committee

Arménio Barbosa, Representant of Scientific Committee

17:50-18:00 – Group Photo

18:30-20:00 – Biophysics Party

Bar do Estudante da Associação Académica da Universidade de Aveiro

SCIENTIFIC SESSION 1

Chairperson: Nuno Santos

TARGETING DENGUE AND ZIKA VIRUS WITH NEW BRAIN- AND PLACENTA-CROSSING PEPTIDE-PORPHYRIN CONJUGATES

Diogo A. Mendonça^(*), Christine Cruz-Oliveira¹, Lorena O. Fernandes-Siqueira², Giuseppina Guida³, Marco Cavaco¹, Vera Neves¹, Sira Defaus³, Ana Salomé Veiga¹, Toni Todorovski³, David Andreu³, Andrea T. Da Poian², Miguel A.R.B. Castanho¹

¹ Instituto de Medicina Molecular João Lobo Antunes, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal.

² Instituto de Bioquímica Médica Leopoldo de Meis, Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

³ Department of Experimental and Health Sciences, Pompeu Fabra University, Barcelona, Spain.

^(*) Email: diogo.mendonca@medicina.ulisboa.pt

Keywords: *Dengue, Zika, Biological Barriers, Peptide-drug conjugates, Antiviral.*

ABSTRACT

World Health Organization has classified flaviviruses, such as Dengue and Zika (DENV and ZIKV, respectively), amongst the viruses posing the greatest public health risk. Due to the global warming, *aedes* mosquito – the flaviviruses transmitting vector – is expanding to new regions of the globe, increasing DENV and ZIKV epidemic potential. Expansion of these viruses is particularly worrying given that no vaccine or effective therapeutic drugs against DENV and/or ZIKV are available on the market. Moreover, DENV and ZIKV can overcome highly restrictive physiological barriers such as the blood-placental and blood-brain barriers (BPB and BBB, respectively), which further hinders the development of new therapeutics. To fill this treatment gap, we designed peptide-drug conjugates formed by covalent attachment of a BBB peptide shuttle and an antiviral porphyrin drug. We synthesized eighteen novel peptide-porphyrins conjugates (PPCs) and tested their activity *in vitro*, both in viral inactivation and BPB and BBB translocation. Cytotoxicity towards pharmacologic relevant cell lines was also studied.

Four PPCs fulfill the selection criteria, evidencing the ability to inactivate both DENV and ZIKV with IC50s ranging between 0.5 and 25 μ M, translocation capacity across BPB and BBB cellular models, and no-cytotoxicity upon all cell lines tested. Furthermore, mechanistic studies reveal that PPCs translocation is dependent on clathrin-mediated endocytosis and Golgi-vesicles trafficking, on both BPB and BBB models composing cell lines. Currently, PPCs-lipid interactions and dynamics are being characterized, to unveil the PPCs antiviral mechanisms.

Overall, peptide-porphyrin conjugation shows to be an innovative and promising strategy to treat flavivirus brain infections.

Acknowledgements: Work supported by the La CaixaHealth Foundation (projectHR17_00409) and by the European Union (H2020-FETOPEN-2018-2019-2020-01 grant n^o 828774).

DESIGN, PRODUCTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ANTIVIRAL PROTEINS TARGETING SARS-COV-2

Susana Parreiras^(*), Carlos H. Cruz¹, Mariana Valério¹, Pedro M. F. Sousa², Cláudio M. Soares¹, João B. Vicente¹, Diana Lousa¹

¹ ITQB NOVA, Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, www.itqb.unl.pt

² iBET, Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica, www.ibet.pt

^(*) Email: s.parreiras@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19 Pandemic, Spike protein (S), Receptor binding domain (RBD), Angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 (ACE2).*

ABSTRACT

SARS-CoV-2 virus is responsible for the current COVID-19 pandemic, which has caused >500 million infections and >6 million deaths (as of April 2022). Despite vaccination efforts, there remains the need to develop strategies to control infection and treat patients. One of the most promising therapeutic targets of SARS-CoV-2 is the spike (S) protein, responsible for the virus' ability to enter host cells. It consists of two subunits: S1, containing a receptor-binding domain (RBD) responsible for binding to the host cell receptor, and S2, that facilitates the membrane fusion [1]. This makes it one of the most promising therapeutic targets [2]. The aim of this work was to design and produce antiviral proteins that can prevent the interaction between the S protein and the host receptor, angiotensin converting enzyme-2 (ACE2) protein, to block infection. First, several antiviral proteins were computationally designed using the Rosetta program based on the interactions between ACE2 and the RBD. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of the three candidates were performed to test their interaction with the RBD, which was followed by their experimental validation. The secondary structure and thermostability of these proteins were tested by far-UV circular dichroism spectropolarimetry. Surface plasmon resonance was used to evaluate the affinity of each candidate for the RBD. Finally, assays using human cells were performed to investigate the ability of the designed proteins to neutralize infection by pseudotyped viruses. The experimental results show that one of the developed proteins is a promising candidate that will be further improved in the future.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through the grant PTDC/CCI-BIO/28200/2017 and Project LISBOA-01-0145-FEDER-007660 (Microbiologia Molecular, Estrutural e Celular) funded by FEDER and FCT, and LS4FUTURE Associated Laboratory (LA/P/0087/2020).

References:

- [1] Jackson GB et al. (2018) Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol 23, 3-20
- [2] Cao L et al. (2020) Science 6515, 426-431

SCIENTIFIC SESSION 2

Chairperson: Paula Gameiro

G-QUADRUPLIX FORMING MOTIFS IN THE PROMOTER REGION OF THE B-MYB PROTO-ONCOGENE: A TARGET FOR CANCER THERAPY?

André Miranda¹, **Anne Cucchiaroni**², **Paula A. Oliveira**³, **Jean-Louis Mergny**^{2*}, **Carla Cruz**^{1*}

¹ CICS-UBI - Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Av. Infante D. Henrique, Covilhã, Portugal;

² Laboratoire d'Optique et Biosciences, École Polytechnique, CNRS, INSERM, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, 91128 Palaiseau, France;

³ Centre for Research and Technology of Agro-Environmental and Biological Sciences (CITAB), Inov4Agro, University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro (UTAD), Quinta de Prados, 5000-801 Vila Real, Portugal;

(*) *Email:* andre.miranda@ubi.pt | jean-louis.mergny@polytechnique.edu | carlacruz@fcsaude.ubi.pt

Keywords: *Lung Cancer, B-MYB, G-quadruplex, Nucleic Acids Biophysics, Cancer Therapy.*

ABSTRACT

Lung cancer (LC) is the leading cause of cancer-related death worldwide with a 5-year survival rate of less than 15%. Thus, novel targets and synergistic therapeutic combinations are needed. B-MYB is a proto-oncogene responsible for encoding a nuclear protein involved essential in the physiological regulation of cell cycle progression. Aberrant expression leads to gene alterations causing tumorigenesis and sustained tumor growth. B-MYB overexpression is commonly observed in several cancers, namely in LC (83%), and is a predictor of poor prognosis. In LC, B-MYB is up-regulated and promotes cell growth, motility and can induce activation of ERK and Akt signaling pathways. Bioinformatic analysis of the genome showed that promoter regions of oncogenes are highly enriched in guanines thus allowing the formation of G-quadruplexes (G4) structures. G4s result from the stacking of two or more quartets; each formed by the self-folding of four guanines in a planar arrangement *via Hoogsteen bonds*. It has hypothesized that G4 can have a gene regulatory function due to being significantly represented around transcription start sites. Targeting the G4 in this region could constitute a novel anticancer strategy as this quadruplex may be recognized by small molecules to suppress oncogene transcription. In this context, the aim of the work was to identify and confirm a G4 structure in the B-MYB gene acting as a target for LC therapy. Thus, we carried out several experiments (bioinformatics and biophysical), such as CD and UV spectroscopy and FRET experiments, to confirm the ability of B-MYB sequences to fold into G4 structures. Our results demonstrate the existence of G-rich sequences in the B-MYB promoter capable to form stable G4 under physiological conditions revealing a promising target for LC therapy.

Acknowledgements: A.M. acknowledges the doctoral fellowship grant from FCT – Foundation for Science and Technology (ref. 2021.04785.BD). This work received financial support from PT national funds FCT/MCTES through CICS-UBI (ref. UIDB/00709/2020), CITAB-UTAD (ref. UIDB/04033/2020), and the Portuguese NMR Network (ROTEIRO/0031/2013-PINFRA/22161/2016). C.C. acknowledges the grant from FCT ref. UIDP/00709/2020. J-L.M. benefited from support from Inserm, INCa G4 Access and ANR (ANR-20-CE12-0023) grants.

SYNCHROTRON-BASED INFRARED MICROSPECTROSCOPY OF NANOPLATFORMS AND SKIN: UNVEILING MOLECULAR INTERACTIONS

Ana Isabel Barbosa^{1,2}, Cláudia Nunes¹, Ibraheem Yousef³, Sofia A. Costa Lima^{1,*}, Salette Reis¹

¹ LAQV, REQUIMTE, Departamento de Ciências Químicas, Faculdade de Farmácia, Universidade do Porto, Rua de Jorge Viterbo Ferreira, 228, 4050-313 Porto, Portugal

² ICBAS School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Portugal

³ ALBA Synchrotron, Carrer de la Llum 2-26, Cerdanyola del Vallès, 08290, Barcelona, Spain

(*) Email: slima@ff.up.pt

Keywords: *keratin, polymeric nanoparticles, porcine skin, skin absorption, skin lipids*

ABSTRACT

The application of nanoplatforms as permeation enhancers in skin drug delivery is a growing research field. However, the mechanisms of interaction with the skin structure are still unknown. Polymeric nanoparticles and hydrogels have demonstrated several physicochemical and biological advantages for skin drug delivery, among which is the enhancement of skin permeation. This study aims to elucidate interaction mechanisms using synchrotron-based Fourier Transform Infrared Microspectroscopy (SR-FTIRM) combined with multivariate analysis and *in vitro* skin permeation assay. Given the molecular weight influence on chitosan's properties, fucoidan/chitosan nanoparticles were produced using low- and medium-molecular-weight chitosan. Chemical maps and spectral analysis revealed that fucoidan/chitosan nanoparticles induced changes in the lipids and protein regions. Inter-sample spectral differences were identified using principal component analysis. Low molecular weight fucoidan/ chitosan nanoparticles caused changes in the skin lipids' lateral packing and structure at the stratum corneum layer towards a less ordered state and higher fluidity, and no evidence was found on proteins structure. The opposite was revealed for medium molecular weight fucoidan/chitosan nanoparticles, which induced changes in the secondary structure of keratin and altered lipid structure to an ordered and dense conformation. *In vitro* permeation assays with Franz diffusion cells correlate with the observed changes in the skin lipid and protein structure with enhanced skin permeation of a hydrophilic molecule incorporated within the fucoidan/chitosan nanoparticles. The findings of this study unveil molecular changes in the skin structure induced by the nanoparticles only possible with the application of the powerful and precise SR-FTIRM technique.

Acknowledgements: This work received financial support from PT national funds (FCT/MCTES) through grants UID/QUI/50006/2020, from the European Union (FEDER funds through COMPETE POCI-01-0145-FEDER-030834) and National Funds (FCT) through project PTDC/QUI-COL/30834/2017. SCL thanks funding from FCT/MEC (CEECIND/01620/2017) financed by national funds. AIB thanks her funding FCT/MEC (SFRH/BD/147038/2019).

SCIENTIFIC SESSION 3

Chairperson: Hugo Louro

POLYSACCHARIDES HYPOCHOLESTEROLEMIC POTENTIAL: FROM STRUCTURE TO FUNCTION

Filipe Coreta-Gomes^(*), Maria João Moreno², Fernanda Machado¹, Cláudia Nunes³, Manuel António Coimbra¹

¹ LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

² Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Coimbra, Rua Larga Largo D. Dinis, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

³ CIGECO-Aveiro Institute of Materials, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

^(*) *Email:* filipecoreta@ua.pt

Keywords: *Polysaccharides, Cholesterol, Sequestration, Bile salts, Structure-function relationships.*

ABSTRACT

Polysaccharides from different sources have been related with hypocholesterolemic potential, and several cholesterol lowering mechanisms have been identified, namely a) sequestration of bile salts at intestinal lumen decreasing cholesterol bioaccessibility, b) increase viscosity at intestinal lumen limiting diffusion of bile salts micelles containing cholesterol and its delivery to intestinal epithelium; c) affect short chain fatty acid production by polysaccharide microbiota fermentation, influencing cholesterol endogenous production at liver. [1] In this work, polysaccharides with different structural features, such as i) non-charged arabinogalactans and galactomannans (coffee), laminarans (algae) and arabinans (apple pomace); ii) positively charged chitooligosaccharides (commercially available); iii) negatively charged fucoidan (algae), were chemically characterized regarding sugar composition and glycosidic linkages. Evaluation of their effect on the sequestration of bile salt (glycodeoxycholic acid, GDCA) and cholesterol bioaccessibility, using an *in vitro* intestinal model was done using quantitative NMR. [2] Regarding non-charged polysaccharides, arabinogalactans, galactomannans and arabinogalactans showed to have bile salt sequestration, contrary to laminarans. Positively charged chitooligosaccharides showed the highest potential to sequester bile salts (negatively charged at physiological pH) and affect cholesterol bioaccessibility, being similar to a pharmaceutical cationic resin currently used as hypocholesterolemic agent. The binding of bile salts to chitooligosaccharides was shown to be dependent both on electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions shown by solid state NMR and zeta potential. Negatively charged fucoidan, also showed to affect bile salt sequestration being this effect higher to less charged polysaccharide. This work highlight polysaccharides structural features and their influence on hypocholesterolemic function, with relevance for the development of functional food and drug delivery fields.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)/MCTES by the project PTDC/QUI-OUT/29373/2017, through national funds (OE), co-financed by the FEDER, by the Operational Program of Competitiveness and Internationalization (POCI), within the PT2020.

References:

[1] I.M.V. Silva, F. Machado, M.J. Moreno, C. Nunes, M.A. Coimbra, F. Coreta-Gomes, Polysaccharide structures and their hypocholesterolemic potential, *Molecules*. 26 (2021) 4559. [2] F.M. Coreta-Gomes, G.R. Lopes, C.P. Passos, I.M. Vaz, F. Machado, C.F.G.C. Geraides, M.J. Moreno, L. Nyström, M.A. Coimbra, In Vitro Hypocholesterolemic Effect of Coffee Compounds, *Nutrients*. 12 (2020) 437.

FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF AN ELECTRON: BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF CYTOCHROME CbcL AND ITS REDOX COMPLEXES IN EXTRACELLULAR ELECTRON TRANSFER

Jorge M. A. Antunes^{1,2(*)}, Marta A. Silva^{1,2}, Carlos A. Salgueiro^{1,2}, Leonor Morgado^{1,2}

¹ Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, Caparica, Portugal

² UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Caparica, Portugal

(*) Email: jma.antunes@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *Extracellular electron transfer, inner membrane associated cytochrome, protein-protein interactions, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, Circular Dichroism.*

ABSTRACT

Exoelectrogenic microorganisms are in the spotlight due to their unique respiratory mechanisms and potential applications in distinct biotechnological fields, including bioremediation, bioenergy production and microbial electrosynthesis. These applications rely on the capability of these microorganisms to perform extracellular electron transfer (EET), a mechanism that permits the bacteria to transfer electrons to the cell's exterior by establishing functional interfaces between different multiheme cytochromes at the inner membrane, periplasmic space, and outer membrane. The multiheme cytochrome CbcL (*c*- and *b*-type cytochrome for low potential) from *Geobacter sulfurreducens* is associated to the inner membrane and plays an essential role in EET to final electron acceptors with a low redox potential, as iron oxides and electrodes poised at -100 mV. CbcL has a transmembrane domain with six helices and two *b*-type hemes, and a periplasmic domain containing nine *c*-type hemes. The complementary usage of different spectroscopic techniques, as ultraviolet-visible, circular dichroism, and nuclear magnetic resonance allowed to structural and functionally characterize the entry gate for electrons into the periplasm of *G. sulfurreducens*. The reduction potential of CbcL was determined, and both the interaction and the electron transfer reaction between CbcL and the periplasmic triheme cytochrome PpcA were studied. The results revealed that CbcL and PpcA form a redox complex in the periplasm and that the electron transfer reaction is thermodynamically favorable. Taken together, this study shows for the first time how electrons are injected into the periplasm of *G. sulfurreducens* and initiate their journey to the cell's exterior.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through the grants PTDC/BIABQM31981/2017 (CAS) and PTDC/BIABQM/4967/2020 (CAS). This work was also supported by national funds from FCT within projects UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 (UCIBIO) and project LA/P/0140/2020 (i4HB). The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Network and are supported by FCT (ROTEIRO/0031/2013 and PINFRA/22161/2016).

SCIENTIFIC SESSION 4

Chairperson: Manuel Prieto

PHASE-SEPARATING FUSED IN SARCOMA UNDERGOES COLD DENATURATION UPON COLD STRESS

Sara S. Félix^{1,2,3(*)}, Douglas V. Laurents³, Javier Oroz³, Eurico J. Cabrita^{1,2}

¹ Associate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Almada, Portugal

² UCIBIO, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Almada, Portugal

³ Instituto de Química Física “Rocasolano”, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Madrid, Spain

(*) *Email:* s.felix@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *fused in sarcoma, liquid-liquid phase separation, cold stress, NMR*

ABSTRACT

Fused in sarcoma (FUS) is a complex prion-like ribonucleoprotein which undergoes liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) in stress conditions, leading to the formation of biomolecular condensates *in vitro* and *in vivo* which are crucial for cellular survival and fitness [1][2]. The mediation of formation of these liquid compartments is usually attributed to the low-complexity and disordered domains of FUS [3]. In our work we questioned the role of the FUS folded domains on the LLPS mechanism and studied the influence of overall conditions on the phase separation of the full-length protein. Using a combination of turbidimetry, differential interference contrast and fluorescence microscopy, and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR), we show that full-length FUS LLPS is highly responsive and tightly regulated by the surrounding condition (e.g. ionic-strength, salts, temperature and pH) and that intrinsic disorder is crucial for the LLPS process. Our results reveal that the folded FUS RNA-binding (RRM) and zinc-finger (ZnF) domains undergo cold denaturation above 0°C, a process that is determined by the conformational stability of the ZnF motif. We hypothesize that under cold shock conditions, cold denaturation might promote FUS self-assembly and LLPS, acting as a fast cellular response to cold stress. Our study provides the first insight on the influence of cold stress on the FUS protein and how phase separation can be structurally regulated in stress conditions.

References:

- [1] C. Chen, et al. (2019) *Molecules*, 24
- [2] S. F. Banani, et al. *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology*, 18, 2017
- [3] K. A. Burke, et al. *Molecular Cell*, 60, 2015

MOLECULAR DETERMINANTS OF THE SARS-COV-2 FUSION PEPTIDE ACTIVITY

Carolina C. Buga^{1 2*}, Mariana Valério¹, Diogo A. Mendonça², João B. Vicente¹, Miguel A. R. B. Castanho², Cláudio M. Soares¹, Ana S. Veiga², Diana Lousa¹

¹ITQB NOVA, Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Oeiras, Portugal

²Instituto de Medicina Molecular João Lobo Antunes, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

^(*) Email: a.buga@itqb.unl.pt | abuga@medicina.ulisboa.pt

Keywords: *SARS-CoV-2, Spike glycoprotein, Fusion peptide, Membrane fusion.*

ABSTRACT

The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) emerged in 2019 and quickly spread worldwide causing the current coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. SARS-CoV-2 is an enveloped virus and its entry into the host cell is mediated by the spike glycoprotein (S-protein). [1] This protein contains key domains for the viral entry mechanism, such as the fusion peptide (FP) which is able to insert into and disturb the host cell membrane promoting the fusion between the host and viral membranes. Despite the FP importance for the viral entry, there is still no consensus among scientists for its exact location within the S-protein, although two main candidate regions have been suggested. [2, 3] To shed light into this matter, we combined computational and experimental approaches to characterize and compare the effect of the two putative FPs. We conducted a systematic analysis of the SARS-CoV-2 putative FPs, using molecular dynamics simulations, to understand how these peptides interact with the membrane. In parallel, we analyzed the behavior of the same peptides in membrane model systems using biophysical techniques. Since both FPs exhibited modest fusogenic activity, we hypothesized that a longer FP or a cooperation among the individual FPs might be necessary to accomplish fusion between the host and viral membranes. Given the crucial role of the FP to viral entry, our work provides relevant insights into the SARS-CoV-2 entry mechanism.

References:

- [1] Walls AC *et al.* (2020) Cell 181, 281-292.e6
- [2] Koppiseti RK *et al.* (2021) J Am Chem Soc 143, 13205-13211
- [3] Basso LG *et al.* (2021) Biochem Biophys Acta 1863, 183697

SOLUTION STRUCTURES OF ATAXIN-3 IN COMPLEX WITH NANOBODIES WITH ANTI-AGGREGATION PROPERTIES

Vieira, Vitor^{1,2}, Manso, José A. ^{1,2}, Sárkány, Zsuzsa^{1,2}, Pereira, Pedro J. B. ^{1,2}, Silva, Alexandra^{1,2} and Macedo-Ribeiro, Sandra^{1,2}

¹*IBMC – Instituto de Biologia Molecular e Celular, Universidade do Porto, 4200-135 Porto, Portugal*

²*i3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto, 4200-135 Porto, Portugal*

ABSTRACT

Machado-Joseph Disease (MJD) is a neurodegenerative disorder, included in the group of polyglutamine (polyQ) diseases, caused by a mutation resulting in the expansion of the polyglutamine tract in the protein ataxin-3 (Atx3). This protein functions as a deubiquitinase and turns pathogenic whenever its polyQ tract exceeds a threshold of 55 glutamines. Enzymatic activity is ensured by the globular Josephin domain (JD), which is followed by a flexible C-terminus tail containing two or three ubiquitin-interacting motifs (UIMs) and the polyQ tract. The JD carries aggregation-prone regions required for the first stage of aggregation, independent of polyQ tract. Macromolecular interaction of Atx3 partners within this region proved to modulate Atx3 aggregation rates. Nanobodies (NBs), the antigen-binding domain derived from camelid heavy-chain antibodies, are promising tools in biotherapeutics. They are also excellent tools to probe protein aggregation due to their high affinity, specificity and stability. NBs targeting Atx3 have been produced and tested as tools to interfere with protein self-assembly. Two of these NBs interact with Atx3 with nanomolar affinity, as determined by isothermal titration calorimetry, and significantly reduce the aggregation of the disease-related form of the protein. To better understand the molecular determinants of the Atx3 interaction with NBs, we determined the solution structures of the Atx3:NB complexes using small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). The structural data provides new clues for the anti-aggregation properties on the selected NBs.

Acknowledgements: This study was supported by FEDER funds through the COMPETE 2020 - Operacional Programme for Competitiveness and Internationalisation (POCI), Portugal 2020; Portuguese funds through FCT in the framework of the projects “PQTools: Molecular tools for Machado-Joseph Disease” (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-031173) and “Institute for Research and Innovation in Health Sciences” (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-007274); European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement ID 952334 “PhasAGE”. The work was also supported by a research grant from National Ataxia Foundation to A.S. The authors acknowledge the support and the use of resources of Instruct. J. Steyaert and E. Pardon (Nanobodies4Instruct, Vrije Universiteit Brussel) are gratefully acknowledged for support and collaboration in the nanobody production.

ENGINEERING OF ELECTRON TRANSFER PROTEINS TO IMPROVE BIOENERGY PRODUCTION

Alexandre Almeida^{1,2(*)}, Marta A. Silva^{1,2}, Pilar C. Portela^{1,2} and Carlos A. Salgueiro^{1,2}

¹ Associate Lab i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, Caparica, Portugal

² UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

(*) *Email:* asa.almeida@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *Bioenergy, Geobacter, extracellular electron transfer, multiheme cytochromes.*

ABSTRACT

The unique respiratory diversity of *Geobacter* bacteria has attracted a lot of attention. The bacteria can couple the oxidation of a large variety of organic compounds to the reduction of diverse electron acceptors located at the cells' exterior by a mechanism called extracellular electron transfer. Examples of acceptors include U(VI), Cr(VI) and electrode surfaces from which electricity can be harvested [1]. For this reason, *Geobacter* bacteria are nowadays explored for electricity production and for bioremediation of contaminated waters. One of the most conserved group of proteins among *Geobacter* is the periplasmic family of triheme α -type cytochromes [2]. The characterization of the most abundant cytochrome from this family (PpcA) in *G. sulfurreducens* and *G. metallireducens* showed significant differences in their functional mechanisms, including the oxidation order of the hemes and the protein's working redox potential range [3]. The two proteins are structural and sequence homologous and differ only by 13 amino acids. Such small difference provided an excellent platform to understand how the electron transfer mechanisms can be modulated for optimal practical applications. Thus, the non-conserved residues of PpcA from *G. metallireducens* were replaced by the correspondent ones from *G. sulfurreducens*. Complementary biophysical techniques were used to evaluate the effect of each mutation on the protein's functional properties. The results obtained revealed how crucial specific residues are for the fine-tuning of the protein's properties and pave the way to the future development of *Geobacter* strains with higher respiratory rates and current densities production.

Acknowledgements:

This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through grants PTDC/BIABQM/4967/2020 (CAS), 2020.04717.BD (PCP), UIDP/04378/2020, UIDB/04378/2020 and LA/P/0140/2020 (i4HB).

References:

- [1] Lovley, DR et al. (2011) *Adv Microb Physiol* 59, 1-100
- [2] Liu, Y et al. (2011) *ChemPhysChem* 12.12: 2235-2241
- [3] Portela, PC et al. (2021) *J Biol Chem*, 29

POSTER SESSION

POSTER LIST:

P1. PROTEIN-LIGAND INTERACTIONS: THE CASE OF HUMIC ACIDS AND LACCASE

Claudia Peralta, Zaida Almeida, Ricardo Lagoa, Daniela C. Vaz

P2. BIOACTIVE POTENTIAL OF MEDITERRANEAN PLANTS: COMPONENT ANALYSIS AND ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES OF OTANTHUS MARITIMUS

Elisa Foulquié, Cristiana Pires, Pedro Cruz, Vânia S. Ribeiro, Maria João Moreno, Margarida Castro, Daniela C. Vaz

P3. TARGETING CD44 AND TFR1 TO BLOCK IRON ENDOCYTOSIS

Marta C. Marques, Ana R. Coelho, Gonçalo J.L. Bernardes

P4. A NATURAL POLYPHENOL AS A PROMISING COMPOUND FOR CANCER TREATMENT

Inês Paccetti-Alves, Jéssica Marques, Catarina Pimpão, Bruno L. Victor, Graça Soveral

P5. FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF A CAGE-IN-A-CAGE PROTEIN SYSTEM

Ana J. Carvalho, Ana V. Almeida, Alice S. Pereira, Pedro Tavares

P6. ENABLING DRUG DEVELOPMENT WITH BIOPHYSICAL TOOLS: MODULATION OF CANCER RELATED TRANSCRIPTION FACTORS INTERACTION WITH CO-ACTIVATORS

Ana R. Lemos, Ana C. F. Paiva, Micael C. Freitas, Filipe Freire, Daniel Schwarz, Pedro M. F. Sousa, Tiago M. Bandeiras

P7. BIOPROSPECTING SCENEDESMUS OBLIQUUS AS A SOURCE OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY LIPIDS

Ana Rita Pais, Joana Batista, Daniela Couto, M. Rosário Domingues, Helena Cardoso, Joana Silva, Bruno Neves³, Tânia Melo

P8. COMPARING THE INTERACTION BETWEEN HUMAN SERUM ALBUMIN AND CLINICALLY APPROVED HIV REVERSE TRANSCRIPTASE INHIBITORS: THE INFLUENCE OF CHEMICAL MODIFICATIONS IN TENOFOVIR STRUCTURE

Andreia F. Costa Tuna, Otávio Augusto Chaves, Zaida L. Almeida, João Pina, Carlos Serpa

P9. MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS OF REFLECTIN-BASED PEPTIDES

Arménio J.M. Barbosa, Arianna Nurrito, Cátia Soares, Iana Lychko, Margarida Dias, A. Cecília A. Roque

P10. THE FORCE REQUIRED TO REMOVE TUBULIN FROM THE MICROTUBULE LATTICE

Joe Howard

P11. ENGINEERED PROTEINS TARGETING SARS-COV-2

Bárbara C. Fernandes, Carlos Cruz, Susana Parreiras, Elísio Silva, Cláudio M. Soares, Manuel N. Melo, Diana Lousa and J. B. Vicente

P12. CHARACTERIZATION OF LIPIDIC MARKERS OF OSTEOGENIC DIFFERENTIATION OF MESENCHYMAL STEM CELLS USING ¹H NMR METABOLOMICS

Catarina S. H. Jesus, Daniela S. C. Bispo, Marlene Correia, Mariana B. Oliveira, João F. Mano, Ana M. Gil

P13. EVALUATION OF MORPHOLOGICAL AND ELASTIC CHANGES ON ERYTHROCYTES AND γ' FIBRINOGEN AS POSSIBLE PREDICTORS OF SURVIVAL IN AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS

Catarina S. Lopes, Ana Catarina Pronto-Laborinho, Vasco A. Conceição, Marta Gromicho, Nuno C. Santos, Mamede de Carvalho, Filomena A. Carvalho

P14. Pa-MAP2 and EcAMP1R4, TWO ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES WITH ANTICANCER POTENTIAL

Constança Pais do Amaral, Sónia Gonçalves, Octavio L. Franco, Peter Eaton, Nuno C. Santos

P15. RE-USE OF CACO-2 MONOLAYERS IN PERMEABILITY ASSAYS – VALIDATION REGARDING CELL MONOLAYER INTEGRITY

Cristiana L. Pires, Catarina Praça, Patrícia A. T. Martins, Ana L. M. Batista de Carvalho, Lino Ferreira, Maria Paula M. Marques, and Maria João Moreno

P16. BIOPHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MECHANISMS OF TRANSFECTION AGENTS FOR THE USE OF EXOSOMES IN GENE THERAPY

Cristiana V. Ramos, Ricardo Cerqueira de Abreu, Patricia A. T. Martins, Hugo Fernandes, Lino Ferreira, Maria João Moreno

P17. BIOPHYSICAL STUDIES OF EXTJ FROM EXTHIJKL: A PORIN-CYTOCHROME COMPLEX CRUCIAL TO EXTRACELLULAR ELECTRON TRANSFER IN GEOBACTER SULFURREDUCTENS

Dalila M. Pedro, Tomás M. Fernandes, Carlos A. Salgueiro, Leonor Morgado

P18. (ONE) MICROSECOND DYNAMICS AND VOLUME EXPANSION IN A SINGLE TURN OF B-HAIRPIN PEPTIDE CHIGNOLIN UPON ULTRA-FAST pH-JUMP

Daniela Amado, Otávio A. Chaves, Rui Loureiro, Zaida L. Almeida, Catarina S. H. Jesus, Carlos Serpa, Rui M. M. Brito*

P19. ENDO- AND EXOMETABOLOME ADAPTATIONS DURING OSTEOGENIC DIFFERENTIATION OF ADIPOSE-DERIVED MESENCHYMAL STEM CELLS

Daniela S. C. Bispo, Catarina S. H. Jesus, Marlene Correia, Mariana B. Oliveira, João F. Mano, Ana M. Gil

P20. 2D CELL-MEMBRANE MIMETIC MODELS AS TOOLS TO UNVEIL THE INTERACTIONS WITH ANTICANCER DRUGS

Daniela Oliveira, Filipa Soares, Salette Reis, Cláudia Nunes

P21. COARSE-GRAIN PARAMETERIZATION OF CERAMIDE FOR THE MARTINI 3 FORCEFIELD

G. Vieira, M. N. Melo

P22. EFFECT OF PEPTIDE-COATED SILVER NANOSTARS ON BREAST CANCER CELLS

Ítala C. Silva, Miguel Peixoto de Almeida, Eulália Pereira, Erin M. Tranfeld, Octavio L. Franco, Nuno C. Santos, Sónia Gonçalves

P23. *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* AS A SOURCE OF LIPID EXTRACTS WITH BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

Batista J., Pais A., Couto D., Domingues R., Cardoso H., Silva J., Neves B., Melo T.

P24. IN VIVO PROTEIN-PROTEIN INTERACTION STUDIES TO ELUCIDATE THE ELECTRON TRANSFER PATHWAYS OF *GEOBACTER SULFURREDUCTENS*

João Martinho, Carlos A. Sagueiro, Leonor Morgado

P25. STUDY OF BIOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COFFEE INGREDIENTS

Maria Inês Bonifácio, Fernanda Machado, Ramiro Almeida, Manuel A. Coimbra, Filipe Coreta-Gomes

P26. ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT METHODS TO CALCULATE PERMEABILITY COEFFICIENTS

Margarida M. Cordeiro, Armindo Salvador, Maria João Moreno

P27. STEM CELL FOOTPRINTING DURING OSTEOGENIC DIFFERENTIATION

Marlene Correia, Daniela S.C. Bispo, Catarina S.H. Jesus, Mariana B. Oliveira, João F. Mano, Ana M. Gil

P28. MODELLING GD-DOTA FOR MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS IN WATER AND IN PRESENCE OF LIPID BILAYERS

Alexandre C. Oliveira, Hugo A. L. Filipe, Armindo Salvador, Rui Sun, Gregory A. Voth, Carlos F. G. C. Galdes, Maria João Moreno, Luís M. S. Loura

P29. BIOPHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE INTERACTION BETWEEN HUMAN SERUM ALBUMIN AND TWO COMMERCIAL AZO FOOD DYES

Otávio Augusto Chaves, Andreia F.C. Tuna, Rui Loureiro, Zaida L. Almeida, João Pina, Rui M.M. Brito, Carlos Serpa

P30. IMPLICATIONS OF AQUAPORIN-3 AND AQUAPORIN-5 ON PANCREATIC CANCER CELL BIOMECHANICS AND CELL-CELL ADHESION

Patrícia M. Silva, Inês V. da Silva, Maria J. Sarmiento, Ítala C. Silva, Filomena A. Carvalho, Graça Soveral, and Nuno C. Santos

P31. THE ROLE OF RuvBL1/2 IN THE ASSEMBLY OF PROTEIN-RNA snoRNP COMPLEXES

Philipp Busse, Ana C. F. Paiva, Pedro M. Matias, Tiago M. Bandeiras, Pedro M. F. Sousa

P32. TUMOR LIPID SIGNATURES DESCRIPTIVE OF ACQUISITION OF RESISTANCE TO ENDOCRINE THERAPY IN AN ENDOCRINE-RELATED BREAST CANCER MOUSE MODEL.

Rita Araújo, Caroline Lamb, Victoria Fabris, Claudia Lanari, Luisa Helguero and Ana M. Gil

P33. ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES AND IONIC LIQUIDS AS PARTNERS AGAINST BACTERIAL INFECTIONS

Ana Rita Ferreira, Ana Gomes, Luísa Aguiar, Lucinda J. Bessa, Mariana Ferreira, Cátia Teixeira, Paula Gomes and Paula Gameiro

P34. THE IMPACT OF SARS-COV-2OMICRON VARIANT ON THE HUMAN ACE2 BINDING: A COMPUTATIONAL STUDY

R. Teixeira, M. Valério, L. Borges-Araújo, M. N. Melo, J. B. Vicente, D. Lousa, C. M. Soares

P35. THE ANALYSIS OF STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS' NDH2 COARSEGRAIN SIMULATIONS MIGHT BE THE BEGINNING TO UNVEIL A FUTURE THERAPEUTICAL TARGET

R. Barriga, M.M. Pereira, M.N. Melo

P36. NON-STRUCTURAL PROTEIN 1 (NS1) AS A DRUG TARGET FOR SEASONAL AND PANDEMIC INFLUENZA

Rui João Loureiro, Andreia Cunha, Nícia Rosário-Ferreira, Rui M. M. Brito

P37. UNFOLDING EXTRACELLULAR ELECTRON TRANSFER MECHANISMS WITH ALPHAFOLD

Tomás M. Fernandes, Jorge M. A. Antunes, Leonor Morgado, Carlos A. Salgueiro

P38. TOWARDS THE DESIGN OF DRUG-LIKE COMPOUNDS THAT BREAK AMYLOID FIBRILS: TRANSTHYRETIN, A CASE-STUDY

Zaida L. Almeida, Elisabete Ferreira, Pedro F. Cruz, Carlos J. V. Simões, Rui M. M. Brito

P39. FUNCTIONALISATION OF HFCVD DIAMOND FOR THE RECOGNITION OF BIOMOLECULES

Nádia E. Santos, Flávio Figueira, Miguel Neto, Samuel Guieu, Jonas Deuermeier, Filipe A. Almeida Paz, Joana C. Mendes, Susana S. Braga

P1. PROTEIN-LIGAND INTERACTIONS: THE CASE OF HUMIC ACIDS AND LACCASE

Claudia Peralta^(*), Zaida Almeida¹, Ricardo Lagoa², Daniela C. Vaz^{1,3}

¹ Coimbra Chemistry Centre, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

² School of Technology and Management, Polytechnic of Leiria, 2411-901 Leiria, Portugal

³ LSRE-LCM-IPLeia & School of Health Sciences, Polytechnic of Leiria, 2411-901 Leiria, Portugal

^(*) Email: claudia.peralta@qui.uc.pt

Keywords: *Laccase, Humic acid, Aggregation, Protein structure, Bioremediation.*

ABSTRACT

Humic acids (HAs) are ubiquitous redox-active substances naturally present in aquatic and soil systems. HAs physically and chemically modify the structure of the soil, with several positive impacts for the environment. Nonetheless, at high concentrations, humic acids present a high tendency to aggregate and form different aggregate species [1]. The aggregation states of HAs can directly influence their bio stimulant power towards soil remediation and plant growth. Therefore, to understand the influence of certain enzymes in the aggregation state of HAs, we have studied the aggregation process of HAs, in the presence and absence of laccase (of fungal origin: *Trametes versicolor*). Laccases are multi-copper oxidases that are widely used in pollutant detection and bioremediation, given their action over pesticides [2, 3]. Nonetheless, when submitted to the variability and complexity of natural environments, laccases may also undergo structural changes and lose enzymatic activity. Thus, to better understand the laccase-humic acid protein-ligand interaction, we have carried out several experiments by DLS (Dynamic Light Scattering), CD (Circular Dichroism), fluorescence and UV-Vis spectroscopy, in the presence and absence of laccase, HAs, copper and of the copper-chelating agent DTPA (diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid). Enzymatic studies were carried out with ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) as substrate for laccase. The protein exhibited structural and functional changes in the presence of DTPA making the enzyme more prone to interact with humic acid and alter the aggregation profile of HAs.

Acknowledgements: Authors acknowledge the financial support of FCT (PTDC/BIA-MIB/31864/2017).

References:

- [1] Dou RN, Wang JH, Chen YC, Hu YY. (2018). The transformation of triclosan by laccase: Effect of humic acid on the reaction kinetics, products and pathway, Environ. Pollut. 234, 88–95.
- [2] Arregui L, Ayala M, Gómez-Gil X, Gutiérrez-Soto G, Hernández-Luna CE, Herrera De Los Santos H, Levin L, Rojo-Domínguez A, Romero-Martínez D, Saparrat MC, Trujillo-Roldán MA, Valdez-Cruz NA. (2019). Laccases: structure, function, and potential application in water bioremediation, Microb. Cell Fact. 18, 1–33.
- [3] Patel N, Shahane S, Shivam Majumdar <R, Mishra U. (2019). Mode of Action, Properties, Production, and Application of Laccase: A Review., Recent Pat. Biotechnol. 13, 19–32.

P2. BIOACTIVE POTENTIAL OF MEDITERRANEAN PLANTS: COMPONENT ANALYSIS AND ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES OF *OTANTHUS MARITIMUS*

Elisa Foulquié^(*), Cristiana Pires¹, Pedro Cruz¹, Vânia S. Ribeiro^{2,3,4}, Maria João Moreno¹, Margarida Castro¹, Daniela C. Vaz^{1,2,5,6}

¹ Coimbra Chemistry Center, Institute of Molecular Sciences (CQC-IMS), Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

² School of Health Sciences, Polytechnic of Leiria, 2411-901 Leiria, Portugal

³ CiTechCare, Centre for Innovative Care and Health Technology, Polytechnic of Leiria, 2411-901 Leiria, Portugal

⁴ GeoBioTec, GeoBioSciences, GeoTechnologies and GeoEngineering, Earth Sciences Department, Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

⁵ LSRE-LCM - Laboratory of Separation and Reaction Engineering – Laboratory of Catalysis and Materials, School of Technology and Management, Polytechnic of Leiria, 2411-901 Leiria, Portugal

⁶ ALiCE - Associate Laboratory in Chemical Engineering, University of Porto, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal

^(*) Email: ireneelisa98@gmail.com

Keywords: *Medicinal plants, Minerals, Antioxidants, Polyphenols, Antimicrobial activity.*

ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants are a source of bioactive compounds with special interest for the life and health sciences. The Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula has a unique wild flora, composed of halophytic plants with great medicinal interest [1]. Endemic species such as *Otanthus maritimus* (“beach lambs”) thrive in these dune environments and are composed of bioactive compounds with relevant antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. The study of the composition and beneficial properties of the *Otanthus maritimus* plant and of its essential oils and bioactive compounds can lead to new applications in the fields of biotechnology, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and material engineering [2]. Thus, we have characterized the leaves of this plant in terms of composition in minerals and essential oils; as well as in terms of antioxidant capacity; total polyphenolic content, and antimicrobial activity against Gram (+) and Gram (-) bacterial species.

Acknowledgements: Authors thank the financial support by FEDER/COMPETE 2020 (RECI/QEQ-QFI/0168/2012, CENTRO-07-CT62-FEDER-002012), Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (UID/QUI/00313/2019), and Rede Nacional de Ressonância Magnética Nuclear.

References:

- [1] Parracho T, Vaz DC, Veríssimo P, Ribeiro V. (2021). Sand-Dune Plants from the Atlantic Coast of the Iberian Peninsula: Features and Applications. In: da Costa Sanches Galvão J.R. et al. (eds) ICoWEFS 2021. Springer, Cham.
- [2] Parracho T, Vaz DC, Veríssimo P, Ribeiro V. (2022). Green biomaterials: Applications of plant-derived biofilms. In: da Costa Sanches Galvão J.R. et al. (eds) ICoWEFS 2022. Springer, Cham.

P3. TARGETING CD44 AND TFR1 TO BLOCK IRON ENDOCYTOSIS

Marta C. Marques^(*), Ana R. Coelho¹, Gonçalo J.L. Bernardes^{1,2}

^(*) *Email:* martamarques@medicina.ulisboa.pt

Keywords: *breast cancer, iron, metastasis, bispecific antibody.*

ABSTRACT

Cancer remains a leading cause of death and morbidity worldwide. Breast cancer (BC) is the most diagnosed form of cancer in women and it is responsible for the highest number of cancer-related deaths. Despite the advances in chemotherapy, the risks associated with current therapies still carry severe side effects and offer limited benefit to the patient. Although the outstanding improvement in survival with the introduction of anti-HER2 therapies in the standard treatment of advanced disease, a significant number of patients with advanced HER2-positive breast cancer will develop metastases during their disease course. Albeit major advances in the understanding of cancer biology and development of candidate therapeutic agents, there remains an urgent need of exploiting innovative therapeutic agents and disrupting novel signalling pathways. Evidence suggests that targeted therapies may provide an original means of selectively modulating diseased breast tissues. Here we propose to validate and develop an unprecedented approach to tackle metastatic BC, by targeting the overexpressed CD44-hyaluronic acid (HA) and the transferrin receptor 1 (TfR1)-transferrin pathways, with a bispecific antibody (bsAb). Since metastasis rely on the epithelial mesenchymal plasticity of cancer cells, and this plasticity requires a change in gene expression, blocking iron endocytosis will block histone demethylation required to unlock the expression of mesenchymal and metastatic genes. We have already identified commercial promising Abs that bind TfR1 and CD44, which have shown tumor cell growth inhibition. We validated the blocking effect of each individual ab selected on the uptake of labelled transferrin and HA to reduce the total cellular content of iron as previously described¹. Intracellular iron and HA contents were assessed using RhoNox-1, a turn-on fluorescent probe for the selective detection of iron(II) and HA-FITC, respectively in well-established models of BC cells .

We strongly believe that through simultaneous disruption of iron signalling and consequently blocking epigenetic changes using a bsAb, we will control the expression of metastasis genes and selective targeting and killing of MBC cells will be achieved.

Acknowledgements: Our collaborators from the Rodriguez Lab, Institut Curie, Paris, France.

Funding: EXPL/MED-QUI/0232/2021, FCT-MES.

References:

¹ Müller, S., Sindikubwabo, F., Cañeque, T., Lafon, A., Versini, A., Lombard, B., Loew, D., Wu, T.D., Ginestier, C., Charafe-Jauffret, E., Adeline Durand, CA., Vallot, C., Baulande, S., Servant, N. and Rodriguez, R. (2020) CD44 regulates epigenetic plasticity by mediating iron endocytosis. *Nat. Chem.* 12, 929–938.

P4. A NATURAL POLYPHENOL AS A PROMISING COMPOUND FOR CANCER TREATMENT

Inês Paccetti-Alves^(*), Jéssica Marques^{1,2}, Catarina Pimpão¹, Bruno L. Victor², Graça Soveral¹

¹ Research Institute for Medicines (iMed.Ulisboa), Faculty of Pharmacy, Universidade de Lisboa;

² BiolSI, Faculty of Sciences, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisbon, Portugal

^(*) Email: ip.alves@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *aquaporins, cancer, inhibitors, permeability, in silico.*

ABSTRACT

Aquaporins are transmembrane protein channels that facilitate the transport of water, glycerol and small solutes driven by osmotic or solutes gradients, and are essential for fluid homeostasis and energy metabolism in the body. However, AQP1, AQP3 and AQP5 appear aberrantly expressed in a wide range of clinical disorders including cancer and therefore their inhibition in tumor cells has been suggested as a novel therapeutic strategy. Most AQPs modulators reported so far are non-selective and toxic, which makes them difficult to be used in in vivo experiments. The urgent need to discover efficient and selective modulators for therapeutical use led us to develop an innovative structure-based in silico computational workflow to identify AQPs inhibitors. The combination of ensemble Molecular Docking, coupled to Molecular Dynamics and Molecular Mechanics Poisson-Boltzmann Surface Area (MM/PBSA) calculations, allows the trustful discrimination between active/inactive compounds with inhibitory effect on AQPs function. From Sigma-Aldrich compound database, we were able to identify one polyphenol (RoT) as a promising AQP inhibitor with proven drug-like properties. For its experimental validation, we investigated its inhibitory effect on AQP1 and AQP3 by measuring water and glycerol permeability of human red blood cells that endogenously express these AQPs, using stopped-flow spectroscopy. Our results showed that RoT strongly inhibits glycerol permeability via AQP3 ($IC_{50} = 6.02 \pm 0.13 \mu M$) and significantly reduces water permeability via AQP1 ($IC_{50} = 22.83 \pm 0.01 \mu M$). Considering the role of AQP1 and AQP3 in tumorigenesis, these promising data warrant further studies to evaluate RoT anticancer properties.

P5. FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF A CAGE-IN-A-CAGE PROTEIN SYSTEM

Ana J. Carvalho(*), Ana V. Almeida, Alice S. Pereira, Pedro Tavares

UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry; Associate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

(*)Email: ad.carvalho@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *Encapsulins; Dps proteins; Protein encapsulation; Iron storage.*

ABSTRACT

While eukaryotes have membrane-bound organelles, prokaryotes mainly rely on protein nanocages/nanocompartments to sequester harmful compounds and specific enzymes in a restricted environment.[1] *Myxococcus xanthus* encapsulin (EncA) is a 32 nm-wide protein compartment composed of 180 identical subunits. This proteinaceous shell encapsulates toroidal ferritin-like proteins, revealing the potential of this protein complex as an enhanced large compartment for iron storage.[2] Native cargo proteins are specifically directed to the EncA lumen through an amino acid sequence present in their C-terminus (TAG), that can be used to target the encapsulation of exogenous proteins.[1] In this work, the EncA-specific encapsulation TAG was fused to the C-terminal of DNA-binding protein from starved cells (Dps) of *Marinobacter hydrocarbonoclasticus*. Dps is a mini-ferritin, with the ability to rapidly oxidase iron (II) to iron (III), consuming O₂ and/or H₂O₂ as co-substrate. Once oxidized at catalytic centers, the iron species are translocated to the protein inner cavity where they are stored in a mineral form. Dps self-assemble into homododecameric 9 nm-wide nanocages.[3] Upon co-expression we successfully encapsulated ~ 8 dodecameric Dps molecules inside EncA forming the EncA:Dps complex, and thus creating an artificial cage-in-a-cage protein system. We confirmed the presence of EncA:Dps by SDS-PAGE and Size-Exclusion Chromatography. Protein's secondary structure was assessed by Synchrotron Radiation Circular Dichroism spectroscopy and the tridimensional structure using Small Angle X-ray Scattering. Catalytic assays confirmed that the encapsulated Dps was functional, allowing the EncA:Dps system to uptake twice the amount of iron compared to EncA, foreseeing novel biotechnological possibilities for this type of complexes.

Acknowledgements: This project was financed by FCT-MCTES through UCIBIO (UIDP/04378/2020) and i4HB (LA/P/0140/2020), PTDC/OCE-ETA/32567/201 (A.J.C.), PD/BD/135477/2017 (A.V.A.), Radiation Biology and Biophysics Doctoral Training Programme – RaBBiT (PD/00193/2012).

References:

[1] Almeida, A. V., Carvalho, A. J. & Pereira, A. S., *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 448, 214188 (2021); [2] Eren et al., *Structure* 30, 1-13 (2022); [3] Guerra, J. P. L., Jacinto, J. P. & Tavares, P., *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 449, 214187 (2021).

P6. ENABLING DRUG DEVELOPMENT WITH BIOPHYSICAL TOOLS: MODULATION OF CANCER RELATED TRANSCRIPTION FACTORS INTERACTION WITH CO-ACTIVATORS

Ana R. Lemos^{1,2} (*), Ana C. F. Paiva^{1,2}, Micael C. Freitas^{1,2}, Filipe Freire^{1,2}, Daniel Schwarz³, Pedro M. F. Sousa^{1,2}, Tiago M. Bandejas^{1,2}

¹ iBET, Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica, Apartado 12, Oeiras, 2781-901, Portugal

² Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Av. da República, Oeiras 2780-157, Portugal

³ Merck KGaA, Frankfurter Str. 250, Darmstadt, Germany

(*) *Email:* ar.lemos@ibet.pt

Keywords: *Surface Plasmon Resonance, Drug discovery, Cancer.*

ABSTRACT

When dysregulated, the hyperactivity of transcription factor (TF) variants 1,2,3,4 with its transcription co-activator is associated with diseases like cancer. Prevention of TF – co-activator triggered gene transcription is an attractive strategy for therapeutic intervention. The deeply buried and conserved lipidation pocket (P-site) of TF is required for a functional protein and susceptible to drug targeting. Besides ligand binding to the P-site, inhibition of TF – co-activator interaction through the co-activator binding domain regions of TF surfaces is also an investigated intervention option.

Employing surface plasmon resonance (SPR) and differential scanning fluorimetry (nDSF) assays, two fully matured compounds, designed and synthesized by our partners at Merck KGaA, were shown to interact with and stabilize all four TF subtypes, with sub-micromolar affinity. Since the transcription co-activator in its full-length is prone to degradation during purification, we have developed an SPR method (Extract2Chip) that bypasses the need for protein purification, through direct immobilization of the biotinylated target from lysed cells on Neutravidin-coated chip surfaces. This strategy allowed us to study the impact of small molecules in the interaction between all TF variants and co-activator. Here we show, for the first time, the TF – co-activator interaction modulation promoted by two different compounds (P-site and TF surface binder), pushing forward the drug discovery campaign for this important therapeutic target.

P7. BIOPROSPECTING *SCENEDESMUS OBLIQUUS* AS A SOURCE OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY LIPIDS

Ana Rita Pais^{1,2,3(*)}, Joana Batista^{1,2,3}, Daniela Couto^{1,2}, M. Rosário Domingues^{1,2}, Helena Cardoso⁴, Joana Silva⁴, Bruno Neves³, Tânia Melo^{1,2}

¹ Mass Spectrometry Centre, LaQV REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Santiago University Campus, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

² Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies, CESAM, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Santiago University Campus, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

³ Department of Medical Sciences and Institute of Biomedicine (iBiMED), University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

⁴ Allmicroalgae-Natural Products S.A., Rua 25 de Abril s/n, 2455-413 Pataias, Portugal

(*) Email: ana.s.pais@ua.pt

Keywords: *microalgae, Scenedesmus obliquus, polar lipids, omega-3, bioactivities, lipidomic.*

ABSTRACT

Microalgae have been recognized as a valuable resource for food, feed, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries. In particular, the polar lipidome of microalgae is very important due to the presence of bioactive polar lipids rich in ω -3 PUFAs, that are more stable and have higher bioavailability. Polar lipids, including phospholipids (PL) and glycolipids (GL), play key structural roles as constituents of extraplastidial and plastidial membranes (chloroplasts and thylakoids), respectively. *Scenedesmus obliquus* is a microalga with high amounts of ω -3 PUFAs esterified in polar lipids, however there are no studies on the bioactivity of its polar lipids. In this work, we evaluated the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant potential of total lipid extracts (TLE) and fractions rich in PL + betaines (PL+BT) and GL. Besides, we correlated the bioactive potential with the polar lipid composition using mass spectrometry. *S. obliquus* had a lipid content that ranged from 7.69% to 11.1%, in which ~83% were GL and ~27% were PL. All lipid extracts showed antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. The lipidomic analysis unveil that GL and PL+BT profiles were similar in fractions and TLE. In addition, some species that have already been reported with bioactivity were identified in the lipid extracts. In conclusion, polar lipids of *S. obliquus* have potential for application in different industries.

Acknowledgements: Thanks are due to the University of Aveiro and FCT/MCT for the financial support to CESAM (UIDP/50017/2020 + UIDB/50017/2020 + LA/P/0094/2020), LAQV/REQUIMTE (UIDP/50006/2020 + UIDB/50006/2020), RNEM (LISBOA-01-0145-FEDER-402-022125) through national funds and, where applicable, co-financed by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement and COMPETE 2020. Authors also thanks to the AlgaValor project, from the Portugal 2020 program (grant agreement n^o POCI-01-0247-FEDER-035234; LISBOA-01-0247-FEDER-035234; ALG-01-0247-FEDER-035234). Tânia Melo thanks the Junior Researcher contract (CEECIND/01578/2020). The authors are also thankful to the COST Action EpiLipidNET, CA19105-Pan-European Network in Lipidomics and EpiLipidomics.

P8. COMPARING THE INTERACTION BETWEEN HUMAN SERUM ALBUMIN AND CLINICALLY APPROVED HIV REVERSE TRANSCRIPTASE INHIBITORS: THE INFLUENCE OF CHEMICAL MODIFICATIONS IN TENOFOVIR STRUCTURE

Andreia F. Costa Tuna^(*), Otávio Augusto Chaves, Zaida L. Almeida, João Pina, Carlos Serpa

Coimbra Chemistry Center – Institute of Molecular Sciences (CQC-IMS), Faculty of Science and Technology, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra, Rua Larga, 3004-535, Portugal

^(*) *Email:* andreia.dacostatuna@gmail.com

Keywords: *Albumin, HIV, Antiretrovirals, Spectroscopy, In silico calculations*

ABSTRACT

HIV is a lentivirus also belonging to the classification of retrovirus. Thus, its genome is composed of two homologous copies of viral ribonucleic acid (vRNA) which will be converted to viral deoxyribonucleic acid (vDNA) by the action of reverse transcriptase (RT). To decrease the virus replication one of the strategies is to inhibit RT activity and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate (TDF) is one of the most common prodrugs for this purpose. Recently Tenofovir Alafenamide (TAF) was approved by FDA due to its lower metabolism in the liver until tenofovir (TFV, easily eliminated of the body). Despite TDF and TAF having chemical similarities, they show different pharmacokinetic parameters (absorption and bioavailability), and curiously they have not yet been evaluated in terms of biophysical profile in presence of the more abundant protein in the plasma that responsible to transport drugs until their targets, human serum albumin (HSA) [1-5]. Thus, to better understand the influence of chemical modifications in tenofovir in the pharmacokinetic the present work reports binding studies of HSA with TFV, TDF, and TAF by UV-visible, isothermal titration calorimetry, steady-state, and time-resolved fluorescence combined with molecular docking. The albumin and the three tenofovir interact spontaneously ($\Delta G^\circ < 0$) and weakly ($K_{sv} \approx 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$), being enthalpically ($\Delta H^\circ < 0$) and entropically ($\Delta S^\circ < 0$) driven. The main fluorescence quenching mechanism of albumin is static. Subdomain IB (site III), where tryptophan is not located, was detected as the main binding pocket. The interactive proportion HSA:Drug is 1:1 ($n \approx 1$) and the temperature impact drastically in the binding capacity of each tenofovir to HSA. Overall, the chemical modification in TFV, TDF, and TAF seen not to impact drastically the binding parameters to HSA indicating that the difference in their pharmacokinetic profile is probably related to their chemical stability and not to their interactive profile with albumin.

Acknowledgements: The Coimbra Chemistry Centre is supported by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT). O.A.C. thanks FCT for his PhD fellowship 2020.07504.BD.

References:

- [1] Haase, A.T. Nature. 322 (1986) 130-136. [2] Dubois, N.; et al. Front. Microbiol. 9 (2018) 527. [3] Tian, L.; et al. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. 115 (2018) 507-508. [4] Mesquita, P. M.; et al. J. Antimicrob. Chemoter. 67 (2012) 1730-1738. [5] Ray, A.S.; et al. Antiviral Res. 125 (2016) 63-70.

P9. MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS OF REFLECTIN-BASED PEPTIDES

Arménio J.M. Barbosa^{1,2(*)}, Arianna Nurrito^{1,2}, Cátia Soares^{1,2}, Iana Lychko^{1,2}, Margarida Dias^{1,2}, A. Cecília A. Roque^{1,2}

¹Associate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

²UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

(*) *Email:* aj.barbosa@fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *Molecular Dynamics Simulations, Peptide, Reflectin, Peptide Assembly.*

ABSTRACT

Reflectins are responsible for camouflage of cephalopods upon environmental stress. These proteins organize in platelets in specialized skin organelles called iridophores and act as a biological Bragg-reflector. The space between reflectin layers contracts upon an external stress-stimulus modifying the reflected light in the animal skin. These proteins are intrinsically disordered with specific highly conserved domains, which are repeated along the sequence followed by variable linkers. Self-assembly mechanism is still not clear; however, it was observed that monomers assemble into nanoparticles of 20-30nm, and the richness in hydrophobic residues suggest that it is promoted by π - π stacking interactions.

A reflectin-based peptide was created taking in consideration the most abundant residues in reflectin's conserved regions. The sequence was analyzed for its propensity in assembling in a β -amyloid structure and three assembly models were obtained. The peptide bundles were edited and curated with Moe using Protein Builder, Structure Preparation and energy minimization tools. Molecular dynamics simulations of the assemblies were performed with GROMACS, and simulation analysis performed using GROMACS and Moe tools.

The simulations analysis indicates that the peptide bundle with an aromatic and hydrophobic core is more stable, in agreement with the rational model predicted from experimental results.

Acknowledgements: This work is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No. 899732 (PURE Project), national funds from FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., in the scope of the project UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 of the Research Unit on Applied Molecular Biosciences – UCIBIO, the project LA/P/0140/2020 of the Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy – i4HB, the projects PTDC/BII-BIO/28878/2017 (LISBOA-01-0145-FEDER-028878), PTDC/CTM-CTM/3389/2021, and the PhD grant SFRH/BD/147388/2019.

P10. THE FORCE REQUIRED TO REMOVE TUBULIN FROM THE MICROTUBULE LATTICE

Joe Howard ^{1,2*}

¹ Gulbenkian Institute

² Yale University

(*) *Email:* joe.howard@yale.edu

Keywords: *Molecular Dynamics Simulations, Peptide, Reflectin, Assembly, β -amyloid structure.*

ABSTRACT

Severing enzymes and molecular motors extract tubulin from the walls of microtubules by exerting mechanical force on tubulin subunits buried in the lattice. However, how much force is needed to remove tubulin from microtubules is unknown, as is the pathway by which subunits are removed. Using a site-specific functionalization method, we applied forces to the C-terminus of α -tubulin with an optical tweezer and found that a force of ~ 30 pN is required to extract tubulin from the microtubule wall. Additionally, we discovered that partial unfolding is an intermediate step in tubulin removal and that the unfolding and extraction forces are similar to those generated by AAA-unfoldases. Lastly, we show that several kinesins can also extract tubulin from the microtubule lattice. Our results provide the first experimental investigation of how tubulin responds to mechanical forces exerted on its α -tubulin C-terminal tail and have implications for the mechanisms of severing enzymes and microtubule stability

P11. ENGINEERED PROTEINS TARGETING SARS-COV-2

Bárbara C. Fernandes^{1*}, Carlos Cruz¹, Susana Parreiras¹, Elísio Silva², Cláudio M. Soares¹, Manuel N. Melo¹, Diana Lousa¹ and J. B. Vicente¹

¹ Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier

² Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica

(*) *Email:* bs.fernandes@itqb.unl.pt

Keywords: *SARS-CoV-2, de novo design proteins, nanoparticle, multivalent-display.*

ABSTRACT

SARS-CoV-2 is the virus responsible for the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic, so far having infected over 500 million people and caused over 6 million deaths. Despite the available vaccines and monoclonal antibodies targeting the virus Spike protein, responsible for viral entry, we still need complementary therapeutic options. To address this, we used a computational design approach to develop antiviral proteins targeting the Spike protein.

Four design proteins: Lead 1, 2, 3 and 4, were expressed in *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) and purified from inclusion bodies. To ensure that they presented the expected fold, the proteins were analysed by circular dichroism (CD). Despite being able to successfully recover the antiviral proteins from inclusion bodies, they displayed impaired stability. Thus, another design was generated: Lead 5. Lead 5 was successfully expressed and from the cytoplasm of *E. coli* cells, and CD spectra analysis matched the predicted fold. Biolayer interferometry was used to measure binding between Lead 5 and the viral target.

To increase the inhibitory efficiency of Lead 5, we designed a nanoparticle where multiple copies of this antiviral protein are presented to the virus. The nanoparticle was firstly validated using Coarse Grain simulations, then expressed in *E. coli* and purified. With this approach, we hope to develop a new therapeutic platform against SARS-CoV-2.

P12. CHARACTERIZATION OF LIPIDIC MARKERS OF OSTEOGENIC DIFFERENTIATION OF MESENCHYMAL STEM CELLS USING ¹H NMR METABOLOMICS

Catarina S. H. Jesus^(*), Daniela S. C. Bispo¹, Marlene Correia¹, Mariana B. Oliveira¹, João F. Mano¹, Ana M. Gil

¹ Department of Chemistry, CICECO - Aveiro Institute of Materials (CICECO/UA), University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal.

^(*) *Email:* catarina.jesus@ua.pt

Keywords: *Metabolomics, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, Mesenchymal Stem Cells, Osteogenesis, Lipids.*

ABSTRACT

In bone tissue engineering, a deep knowledge of the osteogenesis of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) is of critical importance to improve therapeutics for traumatic bone healing and genetic bone diseases. Metabolomics has already contributed to some extent towards the understanding of the osteogenic mechanism of MSCs [1-4]. Nevertheless, studies on the role of lipids metabolism are still scarce [3,4]. This work aims to tackle the lipid changes throughout a 21-day period of osteogenic differentiation of human adipose-derived MSCs (hAMSCs) in 2D culture, using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) untargeted metabolomics. Changes in the intracellular lipid composition of hAMSCs were interpreted based on multivariate and univariate statistical approaches. Our ¹H NMR strategy detected various groups of lipids with statistically relevant changes, such as cholesterol, phosphatidylethanolamine, plasmalogens, sphingomyelins, mono- and polyunsaturated fatty acids, among others. These results may provide new insights for the basic knowledge of MSCs osteogenesis.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) for co-funding the BIOIMPLANT project (PTDC/BTM-ORG/28835/2017) through the COMPETE2020 program and European Union fund FEDER (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-028835); his work was developed within the scope of the project CICECO-Aveiro Institute of Materials, UIDB/50011/2020, UIDP/50011/2020 & LA/P/0006/2020, financed by national funds through the FCT/MEC (PIDDAC). DSB acknowledges the Sociedade Portuguesa de Química and FCT for her PhD grant SFRH/BD/150655/2020. The NMR spectrometer used in this work is part of the National NMR Network, partially supported by Infrastructure Project N^o 022161 (co-financed by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PURL and FCT through PIDDAC).

References:

- [1] Bispo, D. S. C.; et al., *Stem Cell Rev. and Rep.* 2021, 17, 2003–2024.
- [2] Bispo, D. S. C.; et al., *J. Proteome Res.* 2022, 21, 654–670.
- [3] Bispo, D. S. C.; et al., *Cells* 2022, 11, 1257.
- [4] Silva, C. G. D.; et al., *Chem. Phys. Lipids* 2020, 232, 104964.

P13. EVALUATION OF MORPHOLOGICAL AND ELASTIC CHANGES ON ERYTHROCYTES AND γ' FIBRINOGEN AS POSSIBLE PREDICTORS OF SURVIVAL IN AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS

Catarina S. Lopes^(*), Ana Catarina Pronto-Laborinho¹, Vasco A. Conceição¹, Marta Gromicho¹, Nuno C. Santos¹, Mamede de Carvalho^{1,2}, Filomena A. Carvalho¹

¹ Instituto de Medicina Molecular, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisbon, Portugal.

² Department of Neurosciences and Mental Health, Hospital de Santa Maria, Centro Hospitalar Universitário Lisboa Norte, Lisbon, Portugal.

^(*) Email: catarinalopes@medicina.ulisboa.pt

Keywords: *erythrocyte, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, fibrinogen, survival.*

ABSTRACT

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is an aggressive neurodegenerative disorder, affecting motor neurons¹⁻³. It is related with neuroinflammation, which is associated with increased risk of thrombosis⁴. Erythrocytes have a fundamental role in binding to inflammatory mediators. Changes on erythrocytes have severe effects on cell functionality⁵. Erythrocyte aggregation, together with fibrinogen, have pathogenic implications in thrombus formation⁶, promoting thrombotic events⁵. Using atomic force microscopy (AFM), we aimed to study the morphological, biomechanical and biophysical properties of erythrocytes from ALS patients. We also evaluated changes on γ' fibrinogen plasma levels as possible biomarker of ALS, and to test its role as a predictor of disease progression and survival. Our results show that erythrocytes from ALS patients are thicker and have less membrane roughness than those from healthy blood donors. In addition, they are less stiff than the erythrocytes from the control group. The haemorheological parameters of ALS patients seem to be altered, potentially promoting changes on blood flow. Erythrocytes from ALS patients have higher tendency to aggregate. The blood from ALS patients is more viscous. These results could comprise prognostic value given that erythrocytes are very adaptive cells, according to the different pathophysiological conditions. Moreover, there is a link between γ' fibrinogen concentration and survival in ALS patients: patients with higher γ' fibrinogen plasma levels survived longer, and this finding was not influenced by confounders like age, gender, respiratory impairment or functionality (ALSFRS-R score)⁴. Early diagnosis through the identification of ALS biomarkers is the most promising approach in ALS research.

References:

- (1) Kiernan, M. C.; Vucic, S.; Cheah, B. C.; Turner, M. R.; Eisen, A.; Hardiman, O.; Burrell, J. R.; Zoing, M. C. Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis. *Lancet* **2011**, *377*(9769), 942–955.
- (2) Pronto-Laborinho, A. C.; Pinto, S.; de Carvalho, M. Roles of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor in Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis. *Biomed Res Int* **2014**, *2014*(947513).
- (3) Hardiman, O.; Al-Chalabi, A.; Chio, A.; Corr, E. M.; Logroscino, G.; Robberecht, W.; Shaw, P. J.; Simmons, Z.; van den Berg, L. H. Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis. *Nat. Rev. Dis. Prim.* **2017**, *3*(1), 17071.
- (4) Pronto-Laborinho, A. C.; Lopes, C. S.; Conceição, V. A.; Gromicho, M.; Santos, N. C.; de Carvalho, M.; Carvalho, F. A. γ' Fibrinogen as a Predictor of Survival in Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis. *Front. Cardiovasc. Med.* **2021**, *8*(715842).
- (5) Pretorius, E.; Olumuyiwa-Akeredolu, O. O.; Mbotwe, S.; Bester, J. Erythrocytes and Their Role as Health Indicator: Using Structure in a Patient-

P14. Pa-MAP2 and EcAMP1R4, TWO ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES WITH ANTICANCER POTENTIAL

Constança Pais do Amaral¹(*), Sónia Gonçalves¹, Octavio L. Franco^{2,3}, Peter Eaton^{4,5}, Nuno C. Santos¹

¹ Instituto de Medicina Molecular, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, 1649-028 Lisbon, Portugal

² Centro de Análises Proteômicas e Bioquímicas, Pós-graduação em Ciências Genômicas e Biotecnologia, Universidade Católica de Brasília, Brasília 71966-700

³ S-Inova Biotech, Pós-graduação em Biotecnologia, Universidade Católica Dom Bosco, Campo Grande 79117-010, Brazil

⁴ LAQV/REQUIMTE, Departamento de Química e Bioquímica, Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade do Porto, 4051-401 Porto, Portugal

⁵ The Bridge, School of Chemistry, Joseph Banks Laboratories, University of Lincoln, UK

(*) *Email:* maria.paisdoamaral@medicina.ulisboa.pt

Keywords: *Bioactive peptides; breast cancer; anticancer; AFM; zeta potential.*

ABSTRACT

Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer. Despite well-known, the success of its therapeutics is variable, adding the development of resistance and side effects, there is the need for new drug development. Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are small, cationic, naturally produced peptides. Presenting a broad-spectrum of activities, their potential for clinical use has gained relevance in recent years. Often, AMPs require modifications for application improvement. An anti-freezing palindromic analogue peptide, Pa-MAP2, was rationally designed, characterized and tested for antimicrobial activity. Another bioinspired peptide, EcAMP1R4, was also tested, exhibiting activity towards Gram-negative bacteria and affinity to anionic membranes. Several classic AMPs also present anticancer activity, as their mode of action includes electrostatic-driven interactions with anionic membranes, such as those of bacteria and cancer cells. Thus, we aimed to test the possible anticancer activity of Pa-MAP2 and EcAMP1R4 against breast cancer cells. For this purpose, we resorted to three different breast cell lines: a non-tumoral cell line (MCF10A) and two tumoral (MCF7 and MDA-MB-231, the latter being triple-negative). The results obtained after peptide treatment indicate that Pa-MAP2 is not cytotoxic for the non-tumoral cell line, while EcAMP1R4 only decreased cell viability at the highest concentration tested. Both peptides reduced MCF7 cell viability after only 1 h of incubation. However, their effect on MDA-MB-231 cells was minor. These findings were corroborated by atomic force microscopy (AFM) imaging. To further understand why both peptides are more efficient towards one cell line, we studied membrane affinity through surface charge alterations assessed by zeta potential measurements.

P15. RE-USE OF CACO-2 MONOLAYERS IN PERMEABILITY ASSAYS – VALIDATION REGARDING CELL MONOLAYER INTEGRITY

Cristiana L. Pires^(*), Catarina Praça^{2,3}, Patrícia A. T. Martins¹, Ana L. M. Batista de Carvalho⁴, Lino Ferreira^{2,3}, Maria Paula M. Marques^{4,5}, and Maria João Moreno¹

¹ Coimbra Chemistry Centre, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

² Biomaterials and Stem Cell-based Therapeutics Laboratory, Biocant - Center of Innovation in Biotechnology, Cantanhede, Portugal

³ Center of Neurosciences and Cell Biology, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

⁴ Molecular Physical-Chemistry R&D Unit, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

⁵ Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, 3000-456 Coimbra, Portugal

(*) *Email:* clpires@student.uc.pt

Keywords: *Caco-2 cells, intestinal permeability, tight junctions, lucifer yellow, high-throughput*

ABSTRACT

The Caco-2 *in vitro* permeability assay is commonly used in drug permeability screening, being generally accepted as a model for human intestinal absorption. The reference protocol¹ requires 21 days after cell seeding to establish a stable and confluent cell monolayer, which is used in a single permeability assay during the time interval of monolayer stability (up to day 30)². In this work we characterize variations in the cell monolayers tightness over the stable time interval, and evaluate the conditions required for their re-use in additional permeability assays. The monolayer integrity was assessed through TEER measurements, permeability of the paracellular marker Lucifer yellow (LY) and complemented with tight junction protein Zonula occludens-1 staining for morphological studies by confocal microscopy. Over 150 permeability assays have been performed, which showed that manipulation of the cell monolayer in the permeability assay may contribute significantly to the flux of LY, leading to P_{app} values that are dependent on the sampling duration. The assay also leads to a small decrease in the cell monolayer TEER, which is fully recovered when cell monolayers are incubated with culture media for two full days. When this procedure is followed, the cell monolayers may be used for permeability assays on days 22, 25 and 28, triplicating the throughput of this important assay.

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by the Portuguese “Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia” (FCT) through projects UIDB/00070/2020, UIDB/00313/2020, PT2020-PTDC/QUI-OUT/29373/2017, and PT2020-PTDC/DTP-FTO/2784/2014. C. L. P. acknowledges support from FCT through fellowship SFRH/BD/138873/2018.

References: ¹ Hubatsch, I. et al. Nature Protocols 2, 2111-2119, 2007

² BriskeAnderson, M. J. et al Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine 214, 248-257, 1997

P16. BIOPHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MECHANISMS OF TRANSFECTION AGENTS FOR THE USE OF EXOSOMES IN GENE THERAPY

Cristiana V. Ramos^{1(*)}, **Ricardo Cerqueira de Abreu**², **Patricia A. T. Martins**^{1,2}, **Hugo Fernandes**², **Lino Ferreira**², **Maria João Moreno**¹

¹ Coimbra Chemistry Center—Institute of Molecular Sciences (CQC-IMS), University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

² CNC, Center for Neuroscience and Cell Biology, University of Coimbra, UC-Biotech Building, Biocant Park, Cantanhede, 3060-197, Portugal

(*) *Email:* cristianavramos95@gmail.com

Keywords: *Gene Therapy, Exosomes, Transfection agents, Biophysical characterization.*

ABSTRACT

Exosomes are ideal natural nanocarriers due to their biocompatibility, high targeting potential, and potential to encapsulate various biological molecules such as proteins and nucleic acids. In this work, the mechanism and loading efficiency of the commercially available transfection agent Exo-Fect™ is explored using biophysical tools, in contrast with most research in this field focused on cell biology methods which evaluate only the final transfection efficiency. The approach followed is expected to provide important insights that may lead to the design of new transfection agents, with higher efficiency and lower toxicity. To elucidate the mechanism of transfection, the Exo-Fect™ effect on membrane properties was characterized. The fluorescent probes DPH and NBD-C16 (located at the lipid bilayer core and membrane/water interface, respectively) were used to report changes in the membrane fluidity and polarity. The Exo-Fect™ effect on membrane integrity was also evaluated from the rate of CF-SE leakage from exosomes (or CBF leakage from LUVs).

Figure 1 - Effect of increasing amounts of Exo-Fect™ on the release of encapsulated CF-SE (plot A) and on the fluorescence intensity of TMA-DPH and NBD-C16 (plot C). A schematic representation of Exo-Fect™ interaction with exosomes compatible with the results observed is shown in plot B. The final concentration of Exo-Fect™ in plots A is 0.4 % (—), 1.2 % (—) and 4 % (—) and in plot C is 0.5 % (—), 1 % (—) and 2 % (—).

Exo-fec™ alters the membrane properties, leading to the aggregation and perturbations of its barrier properties. Our results suggest a significant contribution from adsorption of the cargo at the membrane surface.

P17. BIOPHYSICAL STUDIES OF EXTJ FROM EXTHIJKL: A PORIN-CYTOCHROME COMPLEX CRUCIAL TO EXTRACELLULAR ELECTRON TRANSFER IN *GEOBACTER SULFURREDUCTENS*

Dalila M. Pedro^{1,2(*)}, Tomás M. Fernandes^{1,2}, Carlos A. Salgueiro^{1,2}, Leonor Morgado^{1,2}

¹ Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, Caparica, Portugal

² UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Caparica, Portugal

(*) Email: dm.pedro@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *Extracellular electron transfer, Geobacter, Porin-cytochrome complexes, AlphaFold, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance.*

ABSTRACT

Geobacter are Gram-negative bacteria capable of removing electrons generated by their cellular metabolism through extracellular electron transfer (EET) [1]. Their ability to exchange electrons between intracellular donors and extracellular acceptors is mainly attributed to the more than one hundred cytochromes disposed along the inner membrane, periplasm and outer membrane (OM) of these bacteria [1]. Particularly in the OM, these electron exchange events are promoted by either cytochrome nanowires or porin-cytochrome complexes [1]. In this work, the protein ExtJ from the OM porin-cytochrome complex ExtHIJKL [2] was characterized by biochemical and biophysical techniques, including site-directed mutagenesis, circular dichroism and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopies. The results showed that recombinant ExtJ (8.3 kDa) forms homodimers *in vitro* via a C-terminal cysteine and is composed by five beta-sheets and one alpha-helix. Based on the model predicted by the AlphaFold neural network, the C-terminal cysteine of ExtJ forms a disulfide bridge with a cysteine residue from the periplasmic side of the ExtI porin, indicating that the formation of homodimers *in vivo* is unlikely. Finally, the putative function of ExtJ in the ExtHIJKL complex was probed by NMR interaction studies with a putative periplasmic partner.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through the following grants: SFRH/BD/145039/2019 (TMF), SFRH/BPD/114848/2016 (LM), PTDC/BIA-BQM-31981/2017 (CAS), PTDC/BIA-BQM/4967/2020 (CAS). This work was also supported by national funds from FCT within projects UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 (UCIBIO) and project LA/P/0140/2020 (i4HB). The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Network and are supported by FCT (ROTEIRO/0031/2013 and PINFRA/22161/2016)

References:

[1] Thomas A. Clarke, *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.*, 66, 56-62, 2022.

[2] Fernanda J. Otero, Chi H. Chan, Daniel R. Bond, *J. Bacteriol.*, 200 (19), e00347-18, 2018.

P18. (ONE) MICROSECOND DYNAMICS AND VOLUME EXPANSION IN A SINGLE TURN OF β -HAIRPIN PEPTIDE CHIGNOLIN UPON ULTRA-FAST pH-JUMP

Daniela Amado*, Otávio A. Chaves, Rui Loureiro, Zaida L. Almeida, Catarina S. H. Jesus, Carlos Serpa, Rui M. M. Brito

CQC-IMS, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

(*)Email: samadodaniela2@gmail.com

Keywords: β -Hairpin, Chignolin, Photoacoustic Calorimetry, Molecular Dynamics, Folding.

ABSTRACT

Understanding single folding steps of peptides is crucial to unravel the key events behind the folding of more complex biomacromolecules. Chignolin (GYDPETGTWG) is a short-length β -hairpin peptide designed as a model to study conformational changes of β -sheet proteins [1-3]. Until now the role of the Tyr2-Trp9 interaction in the folding mechanism was not clear yet. The present work accompanies the peptide structure at specific protonation states by circular dichroism (CD), ultra-fast pH-jump coupled with time-resolved photoacoustic calorimetry (TR-PAC) and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. Together, our results described a comprehensive view of how chignolin starts to fold upon local pH changes and the role of Tyr2-Trp9 in the folding mechanism. The CD data showed that β -hairpin formation displays a pH dependent bell-shaped curve, with a maximum close to pH 6, and a large decrease in β -sheet content in alkaline pH. The principal forces responsible for the stabilization of the peptide were identified as hydrophobic interactions between Tyr2-Trp9 and Tyr2-Pro4. Consequently, protonation of Tyr2 is essential for the stability of chignolin. Folding studies were triggered by laser-induced pH-jumps and detected by TR-PAC. The folding of chignolin, due to the protonation of Tyr2 is characterized by a volume expansion (10.4 mL mol^{-1}), independent of concentration, in the microsecond time range ($1.15 \mu\text{s}$) indicating that under basic pH the lack of a π -stacking interaction for Tyr2-Trp9 (hydrophobic core) result in a more flexible and open 3D-structure, which was reinforced by MD simulations at three different pHs: 4.5, 7.4, and 11.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Portuguese Science Foundation FCT (UIDB/00313/2020).

References:

- [1] S. Honda, K. Yamasaki, Y. Sawada, and H. Morii, "10 Residue folded peptide designed by segment statistics," *Structure*, 12(8) (2004) 1507–1518.
- [2] L. T. Karplus M, A.R. Dinner, "Understanding β -hairpin formation" *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 96 (1999) 9068–9073.
- [3] V. Muñoz, E. R. Henry, J. Hofrichter, and W. A. Eaton, "A statistical mechanical model for β -hairpin kinetics," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U S A.*, 95(11) (1998) 5872–5879.

P19. ENDO- AND EXOMETABOLOME ADAPTATIONS DURING OSTEOGENIC DIFFERENTIATION OF ADIPOSE-DERIVED MESENCHYMAL STEM CELLS

Daniela S. C. Bispo^(*), Catarina S. H. Jesus¹, Marlene Correia¹, Mariana B. Oliveira¹, João F. Mano¹, Ana M. Gil¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, CICECO - Aveiro Institute of Materials (CICECO/UA), University of Aveiro, Campus Universitario de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal.

^(*) Email: d.bispo@ua.pt

Keywords: *mesenchymal stem cells, osteogenic differentiation, NMR spectroscopy, endometabolome, exometabolome.*

ABSTRACT

The regeneration of large bone defects remains an orthopedic challenge that is significantly enhanced in advanced aging. Strategies involving mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) are promising alternatives to conventional bone grafts. Because metabolic changes seem critical for bone regeneration, metabolomics may unveil novel information on MSCs osteogenic differentiation,^{1,2} allowing their behavior to be understood and potentially guided towards osteogenic commitment.³ However, only a few reports monitored osteogenesis (with mass spectrometry predominating compared to nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy), with scarce information combining intra- and extracellular adaptations.⁴ Here, NMR metabolomics was applied to monitor endo- and exometabolome changes of MSCs throughout 21 days of osteogenesis. Endometabolome results revealed significant fluctuations in the metabolism of amino acids, energy-related compounds, nucleotides, and anti-oxidative mechanisms. Also, exometabolome data highlighted alanine, glutamate, glycerol and citrate as important secretome components. Different stages of osteogenesis are suggested, supported by putative explanations. Overall, this work shows the great potential of NMR to characterize the dynamic metabolism of MSCs osteogenesis, ultimately enabling the potential discovery of universal biomarkers of osteogenic differentiation efficacy, with potential translation to clinical practice.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge the Portuguese FCT for co-funding the BIOIMPLANT project (PTDC/BTM-ORG/28835/2017) through the COMPETE2020 program and European Union fund FEDER (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-028835); CICECO-Aveiro Institute of Materials project (UIDB/50011/2020 & UIDP/50011/2020), financed by national funds through the FCT/MEC and when appropriate co-financed by FEDER under the PT2020. DSB acknowledges the SPQ/FCT for her PhD grant SFRH/BD/150655/2020. The NMR spectrometer used is part of the National NMR Network, partially supported by Infrastructure Project N^o 022161 (co-financed by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORN and FCT through PIDDAC).

References: [1] Loeffler, J. et al., Trends Endocrinol. Metab. 2018, 29, 99–110. [2] Bispo, D.S.C. et al., Stem Cell Rev. Reports. 2021, 17, 2003–2024. [3] Alakpa, E.V. et al., Chem. 2016, 1, 298–319. [4] Surrati, A. et al., Cell. Physiol. Biochem. 2021, 55, 311–326.

P20. 2D CELL-MEMBRANE MIMETIC MODELS AS TOOLS TO UNVEIL THE INTERACTIONS WITH ANTICANCER DRUGS

Daniela Oliveira^(*), Filipa Soares¹, Salette Reis¹, Cláudia Nunes¹

¹ LAQV, REQUIMTE, Departamento de Química, Faculdade de Farmácia da Universidade do Porto

(*) *Email:* up201808870@up.pt

Keywords: *Biophysics, Langmuir Monolayers, Tamoxifen, Epigallocatechin-3-gallate, Cancer cells membranes.*

ABSTRACT

The combination of conventional anticancer drugs with bioactive compounds has been investigated to create an innovative cancer treatment. Tamoxifen (TAM) is a molecule used in the treatment of breast cancer and epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG) is a polyphenolic compound with anticancer activity. Although other mechanisms of action are also known, evidence suggests that both molecules interact with the plasma membrane, which may explain some of their activities

Thus, in this work, the interactions of EGCG and/or TAM with Langmuir monolayers composed of 1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phospho-L-serine (DPPS), 1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC), sphingomyelin (SM), and cholesterol (Chol) were investigated to obtain the scenario of the interactions between drugs and lipid models of some regions/domains of the cell membranes. Both π/A isotherms and Brewster angle microscopy (BAM) images were gathered.

From the interaction studies with normal cell membranes models (DPPC, SM:Chol (1:1), DPPC:SM:Chol (1:1); pH 7.4), it was shown that both EGCG and TAM intercalate in the monolayers: EGCG, having a strong affinity to DPPC, caused fluidization of the monolayers, while TAM showed affinity to Chol-enriched domains and caused condensation of the monolayers, which may be associated with the side effects of this drug. The affinity of EGCG with DPPC membranes might be the explanation for its pleiotropic effects. Using cancer cell membrane models (DPPS, DPPS:DPPC (1:1) and DPPS:Chol (1:1); pH 6.4), TAM also decrease the monolayer fluidity, but EGCG did not show significant interaction. Thus, the mechanism of action of TAM can be related to the decrease in the cancer cell division, due to membrane condensation.

P21. COARSE-GRAIN PARAMETERIZATION OF CERAMIDE FOR THE MARTINI 3 FORCEFIELD

G. Vieira^(*), M. N. Melo¹

¹ Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Lisbon, Portugal

^(*) *Email:* gm.vieira@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *Ceramide, Martini 3, Coarse-Grain*

ABSTRACT

Ceramides (CERs) are a class of lipids among the least polar ones that has been found in different locations such as the Stratum Corneum, the skin's outermost layer, and the mitochondrial outer membrane. Within the latter, CERs have been linked to the formation of large protein permeable pores, which allow the release of proapoptotic proteins, upon regulated cell death.

Since the release of the new Martini 3 Forcefield, no parameters have been published for CERs, despite its wide relevance. To fulfill this gap, we are developing new parameters for CERs headgroup to be used in Coarse-Grain (CG) simulations with this updated forcefield.

Fully atomistic simulations of either CER headgroup alone in water, or the whole C16-CER in a bilayer of 1,2-dipalmitoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC), or 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DOPC), have been employed to obtain reference data. Headgroup beads have been assigned according to the rules of Martini 3, while ensuring the same hydrophobic/hydrophilic character and solvent accessible surface area (SASA) of the reference data. Tails' beads were assigned alike DPPC ones, which have already been validated, due to its similarities. CG mappings of the atomistic simulations were furtherly performed to develop topology parameters so that CG distances, angles, and dihedrals of the headgroup matched those from reference data. Measurements of area per lipid and melting temperature have also been applied to furtherly validate the parameters.

Our preliminary results show that the developed parameters greatly resemble the atomistic behavior, which, when fully validated, will constitute a remarkable tool for a plethora of membranal CG simulations.

Acknowledgements: FCT (FUNDAÇÃO PARA A CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA), ITQB (MOSTMICRO).

P22. EFFECT OF PEPTIDE-COATED SILVER NANOSTARS ON BREAST CANCER CELLS

Ítala C. Silva¹, Miguel Peixoto de Almeida², Eulália Pereira², Erin M. Tranfeld³, Octavio L. Franco^{4,5,6}, Nuno C. Santos¹, Sónia Gonçalves¹

¹ Instituto de Medicina Molecular, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisbon, Portugal

² LAQV/REQUIMTE, Departamento de Química e Bioquímica, Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal

³ Electron Microscopy Facility, Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciência, Oeiras, Portugal

⁴ Centro de Análises Proteômicas e Bioquímicas, Pós-graduação em Ciências Genômicas e Biotecnologia, Universidade Católica de Brasília, Brasília, DF, Brazil

⁵ Programa de Pós-Graduação em Patologia Molecular, Universidade de Brasília, Brasília, DF, Brazil

⁶ S-Inova Biotech, Pós-graduação em Biotecnologia, Universidade Católica Dom Bosco, Campo Grande, MS, Brazil

Keywords: *Antimicrobial peptides, Silver nanostar, Drug delivery, breast cancer, tumor targeting.*

ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) have been identified as promising alternatives to the conventional molecules used nowadays against infection. Some of them have been shown to have dual activity, both as antimicrobial and anticancer peptides. Silver nanoparticles have been used as improved drug delivery systems and as therapeutic agents. In the present work, we synthesized star-shaped silver nanoparticles (AgNSs) and coated them with the AMP Pa-MAP 1.9, to improve peptide efficacy against cancer cells. To determine the concentration and size distribution of AgNSs we used transmission electron microscopy (TEM), nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) and dynamic light scattering (DLS). The particle surface characteristics and charge were evaluated by zeta potential measurements and UV-visible spectroscopy. AgNSs, Pa-MAP 1.9 and peptide-coated silver nanostars anticancer activity was assessed through a viability test. The nanoparticle synthesis produced stable AgNSs with negative net charge. TEM micrographs and DLS showed AgNSs with similar morphology and size. Peptide-coated nanostars showed consistent size and stability. AgNSs are able to induce cell death in cancer cells at low concentrations and the peptide itself exhibits no cytotoxic activity on these cells. When the peptide is combined with AgNSs, an enhancement of the percentage of cell death was observed. The peptide and the nanoparticles were screened for cytotoxic effects in healthy breast cells as well. Pa-MAP 1.9 has cytotoxic effects in healthy cells, but the peptide-coated nanostars display lower cytotoxicity to healthy cells in comparison with the peptide itself. Thus, Pa-MAP 1.9-coated AgNSs provides lower toxicity and improved anticancer activity.

Acknowledgements: I.C.S. acknowledge FCT-MCTES fellowship PD/BD/136880/2018.

References:

(1) Felício, M. R.; Silva, O. N.; Gonçalves, S.; Santos, N. C.; Franco, O. L. Peptides with Dual Antimicrobial and Anticancer Activities. *Front. Chem.* 2017, 5 (Feb), 5. | (2) Makowski, M.; Silva, Í. C.; Pais do Amaral, C.; Gonçalves, S.; Santos, N. C. Advances in Lipid and Metal Nanoparticles for Antimicrobial Peptide Delivery. *Pharmaceutics* 2019, 11 (11), 588.

P23. *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* AS A SOURCE OF LIPID EXTRACTS WITH BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

Batista J.^{1,2,3}, Pais A.^{1,2,3}, Couto D.^{1,2}, Domingues R.^{1,2}, Cardoso H.⁴, Silva J.⁴, Neves B.³, Melo T.^{1,2}

¹ Mass Spectrometry Centre, LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Santiago University Campus, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

² Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies, CESAM, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Santiago University Campus, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

³ Department of Medical Sciences and Institute of Biomedicine (iBiMED), University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

⁴ Allmicroalgae - Natural Products S.A., Rua 25 de Abril s/n, 2445-413 Pataias, Portugal

(*) Email: joanabatista28@ua.pt

Keywords: *Microalgae, Phaeodactylum tricornutum, omega-3 fatty acids, polar lipids, bioactivity.*

ABSTRACT

Phaeodactylum tricornutum is a diatom with a high content of omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), such as acid eicosapentaenoic (EPA), and small amounts of docosahexaenoic acid (DHA). These omega-3 PUFAs are valuable nutraceuticals, which are mainly esterified on glycolipids and phospholipids. These lipids are components of the extraplastidial and plastidial membranes (chroloplasts and thylakoids), respectively, and the regulation of their composition is very important for the maintenance of the properties of these membranes^{1,2}. However, omega-3 PUFAs are also well-known for their health benefits, namely in preventing inflammation-related non-communicable diseases³. Polar lipids from *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* are the main carriers of omega-3 PUFAs. It has been reported in the literature that omega-3 esterified in polar lipids are more bioavailable than those esterified in triacylglycerides, which is crucial for the biological activity⁴. Nevertheless, the polar lipid composition and bioactive properties as well as the health benefits of this microalga remains scarcely studied, namely the glycolipid- and phospholipid-rich extracts. Therefore, the aims of this work are (a) bioprospecting the total lipid extracts of *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* obtained using ethanol (a food grade solvent) combined ultra-assisted extraction (UAE) and both the glycolipid-enriched and phospholipid-enriched fractions as source of add-value polar lipids with bioactive properties and (b) correlate the bioactive potential with the polar lipid composition, obtained using a high-throughput untargeted lipidomic approach for a comprehensive identification and characterization of the polar lipid profile.

Acknowledgements: Thanks are due to the University of Aveiro and FCT/MCT for the financial support to CESAM (UIDP/50017/2020 + UIDB/50017/2020 + LA/P/0094/2020), LAQV/REQUIMTE (UIDP/50006/2020 + UIDB/50006/2020), RNEM (LISBOA-01-0145-FEDER-402-022125) through national funds and, where applicable, co-financed by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement and COMPETE 2020. Authors also thanks to the AlgaValor project, from the Portugal 2020 program (grant agreement n^o POCI-01-0247-FEDER-035234; LISBOA-01-0247-FEDER-035234; ALG-01-0247-FEDER-035234). Tânia Melo thanks the Junior Researcher contract (CEECIND/01578/2020). The authors are also thankful to the COST Action EpiLipidNET, CA19105-Pan-

P24. *IN VIVO* PROTEIN-PROTEIN INTERACTION STUDIES TO ELUCIDATE THE ELECTRON TRANSFER PATHWAYS OF *GEOBACTER SULFURREDUCTENS*

João Martinho^{1,2(*)}, Carlos A. Salgueiro^{1,2}, Leonor Morgado^{1,2}

¹ Associate Laboratory i4HB Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, Caparica, Portugal

² UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Caparica, Portugal

(*) *Email:* ja.martinho@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *Bacterial two-hybrid system, Electron transfer pathways, Geobacter sulfurreducens, Cytochrome, Redox partners.*

ABSTRACT

Geobacter bacteria are able to reduce toxic and radioactive metals, as well as electrodes outside the cell, in a mechanism known as extracellular electron transfer. This mechanism relies on the interaction between cytochromes from different cell localizations as the inner membrane, periplasm, or outer membrane. The proteins involved on specific routes for reduction of diverse terminal electron acceptors have been pinpointed. However, the specific redox partners haven't been identified. Bacterial two-hybrid systems have been widely used for the recognition of interacting proteins in their cellular native environment. A β -galactosidase based assay that has been validated for the detection of transient interactions as the ones observed between electron transfer proteins will be used to elucidate *Geobacter sulfurreducens* respiratory chains. In this assay, two target proteins are fused to two non-functional but complementing β -galactosidase truncations. The enzyme activity will depend on the interaction between the proteins of interest and can be detected by o-nitrophenol-beta-galactoside (ONPG) hydrolysis. We are using different molecular biology approaches for the preparation of the chimeric plasmids necessary for insertion in *E. coli* MC1061 (which lacks the entire lacZ locus) for the complementation assay. The results obtained until now for the interactions between the inner membrane associated proteins and the most abundant periplasmic ones will be presented.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia through the grants PTDC/BIA-BQM/4967/2020 (CAS) and EXPL/BIA-BQM/0770/2021 (LM). This work was also supported by national funds from FCT within projects UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 (UCIBIO) and project LA/P/0140/2020 (i4HB).

P25. STUDY OF BIOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COFFEE INGREDIENTS

Maria Inês Bonifácio^{1(*)}, Fernanda Machado¹, Ramiro Almeida², Manuel A. Coimbra¹, Filipe Coreta-Gomes¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, 3810-193, Aveiro

² IBIMED, Department of Medical Sciences, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro

(*) *Email:* minesbbonifacio@ua.pt

Keywords: *Coffee, Biophysical properties, Antioxidant activity, Hypocholesterolemic effect.*

ABSTRACT

Coffee is a very well-known beverage whose constituents can vary depending on processing parameters, such as roasting and grinding, and have been involved with health benefits. [1, 2] In this work, coffee as well as its fractionated ingredients were studied regarding their antioxidant and hypocholesterolemic biophysical properties. For this purpose, coffee brews with different roasting degrees (light, medium and dark) and grinding (fine and coarse) were dialyzed to separate low (LMWM) from high molecular weight material (HMWM). The analysis of LMWM fraction showed that it contains mostly free chlorogenic acids (CGAs), while HMWM contains polysaccharides (arabinogalactans, AG; galactomannans, GM) and melanoidins, which were obtained by sequential ethanolic precipitations.

Different roasting degrees showed coffee brews with a similar antioxidant potential (EC₅₀ 0.24 mg/mL). For HMWM, melanoidins showed the highest antioxidant activity, similar to free LMW compounds (EC₅₀ 0.21 mg/mL). The hypocholesterolemic effect showed that light and medium roasted-fine brews were more effective in decreasing cholesterol bioaccessibility (42 and 43%) than dark (30%). HMW fractions obtained from dark-coarse coffee had higher hypocholesterolemic activity, with melanoidins presenting the greatest activity. Bile salt sequestration by HMWM was shown to be the main mechanism influencing the decrease of cholesterol bioaccessibility.

These results allow a better understanding of the biophysical properties of coffee compounds and their effect on health.

Acknowledgements: This work received FCT/MCTES funding through QOPNA (FCT UID/QUI/00062/2019), LAQV-REQUIMTE (UIDB/50006/2020), Machado acknowledge PhD fellowship (2020.06768.BD), the Portuguese NMR Network, project PTDC/QUI-OUT/29373/2017 through national funds (OE) and co-financed by the FEDER by the Operational Program of Competitiveness and Internationalization (POCI), within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement, including Coreta-Gomes research contract. Project 007630 UID/QUI/00062/2019, co-funded by COMPETE2020-UE supported CQC research unit. NMR data was acquired in the UC-NMR facility. Coffee roaster company FEB (Taveiro, Coimbra) for providing coffee samples.

References: [1] Farah, A. Coffee Consumption and Health Implications. in *Coffee* P001-P004 (Royal Society of Chemistry, 2019). doi: 10.1039/9781788015028-FP001

P26. ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT METHODS TO CALCULATE PERMEABILITY COEFFICIENTS

Margarida M. Cordeiro^(*), Armindo Salvador^{1,2,3}, Maria João Moreno^{1,2}

¹ Coimbra Chemistry Centre-Institute of Molecular Sciences (CQC-IMS), Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal

² Centro de Neurociências e Biologia Celular, Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal

³ Instituto de Investigação Interdisciplinar, Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal

(*) *Email*: mmc.margarida0@gmail.com

Keywords: *membrane permeation, kinetic modelling, permeation of weak acids, liposomes.*

ABSTRACT

Unassisted permeation through biomembranes is of utmost importance for the availability of drugs and biological ligands at their target site. The pH variation assay is one of the few methodologies appropriated to characterise the permeation of non-fluorescent weak acids/bases. Permeability coefficients are obtained by following the dynamics of a pH fluorescent probe. Current protocols of this assay only focus on the study of the fast generation of the pH gradient and have raised several concerns which are preventing its generalised use. To transform this assay into a reliable tool, we developed a detailed kinetic model that allowed us to identify the experimental conditions needed to warrant an accurate characterisation of the dynamics of the weak acid/base permeation from the fluorescence variation and evaluate different methods to obtain their permeability coefficient (Figure 1).¹ The results showed that the often-used expression $P_{app}^r = \beta r/3$ is inapplicable to very large or very small vesicles, to moderately or highly lipophilic solutes, or when the development of a significant pH gradient opposes the solute's flux. We anticipate that the resolution of all these concerns and the study of the fast generation and slow dissipation of the pH gradient can turn the pH variation into an important tool to analyse and better understand the general rules of unassisted permeation through biomembranes.

Figure 1. A) Kinetic scheme for the permeation of a weak acid through lipid membranes. B) Validity domains of the simplified procedure usually followed to calculate permeability coefficients from solute dynamics.

Acknowledgements: Work financed by COMPETE 2020, under projects UIDB/00313/2020, UIDP/00313/2020 and UIDB/04539/2020.

References:

[1] Cordeiro, M. M., Salvador, A. & Moreno, M. J. Calculation of Permeability Coefficients from Solute Equilibration Dynamics: An Assessment of Various Methods. *Membranes*. **12**, 254 (2022).

P27. STEM CELL FOOTPRINTING DURING OSTEOGENIC DIFFERENTIATION

Marlene Correia^{1(*)†}, Daniela S.C. Bispo^{1,†}, Catarina S.H. Jesus¹, Mariana B. Oliveira¹, João F. Mano¹, Ana M. Gil¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, CICECO – Aveiro Institute of Materials (CICECO/UA), University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal;

[†] Authors who contributed equally for this work; ^(*) *Email*: marlene24@ua.pt

Keywords: *mesenchymal stem cells, osteogenic differentiation, metabolomics, NMR, exometabolome.*

ABSTRACT

To respond to the clinical demand arising from the shortage of suitable autograft materials, there has been an increasing interest in developing tissue-engineered bone grafts. Thus, the improved understanding of stem cell (SC) osteogenic differentiation and associated metabolic adaptations is of great relevance. Metabolomics is an enticing approach to achieve this and its application to SC research has been recently reviewed¹, highlighting the importance of both cell fingerprinting and footprinting studies. In particular, metabolic footprinting represents the monitoring of the metabolites in the exometabolome, either consumed from or secreted into culture media, offering a non-destructive characterization of SC metabolism. However, most of SC metabolomic studies have focused on the analysis of the intracellular metabolites² and to obtain a more complete picture of cell metabolism, there is a need to articulate both types of studies. In this work, NMR metabolomics was applied to study the footprinting characteristics of osteogenic differentiation of adipose derived-SCs, following up on a recent report of our own³. The metabolic variations throughout the 21 days of differentiation were investigated in cell conditioned-media, and naturally linked to the intracellular metabolism information existing in the literature²⁻³. Undifferentiated control cells were also analyzed to assess the contribution of cell aging metabolism towards the overall exometabolome changes. In addition, different donors were used and compared, for the first time to our knowledge, so that the metabolic alterations associated with donor origin may also be considered, for the definition of osteogenic-specific, donor-independent, metabolic markers of osteogenic differentiation.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) for co-funding the BIOIMPLANT project (PTDC/BTM-ORG/28835/2017) through the COMPETE2020 program and European Union fund FEDER (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-028835); CICECO – Aveiro Institute of Materials project (UIDB/50011/2020, UIDP/50011/2020 & LA/P/0006/2020), financed by national funds through the FCT/MEC (PIDDAC). DSB acknowledges her PhD grant SFRH/BD/150655/2020. The NMR spectrometer used in this work is part of the National NMR Network, partially supported by Infrastructure Project N^o 022161 (co-financed by FEDER through COMPETE2020, POCI and PORL, and FCT through PIDDAC).

References: ¹ Bispo, D.S.C. et al., *Stem Cell Rev. and Rep.* 17, 2003-2024 (2021); ² Bispo, D.S.C. et al., *J. Proteome Res.* 21, 654-670 (2022); ³ Bispo, D.S.C. et al., *Cells.* 11, 1257 (2022)

P28. MODELLING Gd-DOTA FOR MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS IN WATER AND IN PRESENCE OF LIPID BILAYERS

Alexandre C. Oliveira^{1*}, Hugo A. L. Filipe^{1,2}, Armindo Salvador³, Rui Sun⁴, Gregory A. Voth⁵, Carlos F. G. C. Geraldes^{1,6}, Maria João Moreno^{1,3}, Luís M. S. Loura^{1,3,7}

¹ Coimbra Chemistry Center - Institute of Molecular Sciences (CQC-IMS), University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

² CPIRN-IPG—Center of Potential and Innovation of Natural Resources, Polytechnic Institute of Guarda, 6300-559 Guarda, Portugal

³ CNC—Center for Neuroscience and Cell Biology, University of Coimbra, P-3004-517 Coimbra, Portugal

⁴ Department of Chemistry, The University of Hawai'i, Manoa, Honolulu, Hawaii 96822, USA

⁵ Department of Chemistry, James Franck Institute, and Institute for Biophysical Dynamics, The University of Chicago, Chicago, Illinois 60637, USA

⁶ Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Calçada Martim de Freitas, 3000-393 Coimbra, Portugal

⁷ Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Coimbra, P-3000-548 Coimbra, Portugal

(*) *Email:* ac_oliveira10@hotmail.com

Keywords: *Contrast Agents, Parametrization, Membrane Permeation, Molecular Dynamics*

ABSTRACT

The correct parametrization of lanthanide complexes is of utmost importance for their characterization using computational tools such as molecular dynamics simulations, allowing the optimization of the properties for a wide range of applications, including medical imaging. Here we present a systematic study to establish the best strategies for the correct parametrization of lanthanide complexes using the Gd-DOTA as reference, which is used as contrast agent in MRI. We chose the bonded model to parameterize the lanthanide complexes, this being especially important when considering the study of the complex as whole (e.g., for the study of the dynamics of its interaction with proteins or membranes). Adjustment of the Lennard-Jones parameters of the metal was required. The final topologies were able to reproduce ion to oxygen distance (IOD), vibrational frequencies and other structural properties. For the first time, we report the correct assessment of the mean residence time (τ_m) of the coordinated inner sphere water by recording the dissociative events over up to 10 μ s all-atom simulations. The analysis is extended to exchange kinetics of the second coordination sphere, allowing the quantitative characterization of its contribution to the overall water relaxivity.¹ With the correct description of the Gd-DOTA, we studied its interaction with a POPC membrane by means of unbiased simulations to understand its membrane location and interactions. Biased simulations have also been performed to obtain the Potential of Mean Force (PMF) across the bilayer normal and calculate the partition to and the rate of permeation through biomembranes.

References:

[1] Oliveira, A. C.; Filipe, H. A. L.; Ramalho, J. P. P.; Salvador, A.; Geraldes, C. F. G. C.; Moreno, M. J.; Loura, L. M. S.; Modeling Gd³⁺ Complexes for Molecular Dynamics simulations - Towards a Rational Optimization of MRI Contrast Agents (Submitted)

P29. BIOPHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE INTERACTION BETWEEN HUMAN SERUM ALBUMIN AND TWO COMMERCIAL AZO FOOD DYES

Otávio Augusto Chaves^(*), Andreia F.C. Tuna, Rui Loureiro, Zaida L. Almeida, João Pina, Rui M.M. Brito, Carlos Serpa

Coimbra Chemistry Center – Institute of Molecular Sciences (CQC-IMS), Faculty of Science and Technology, Department of Chemistry, University of Coimbra, Rua Larga, 3004-535, Portugal

^(*) *Email:* otavioaugustochaves@gmail.com

Keywords: *Albumin, Food dyes, Azo dyes, Spectroscopy, In silico calculations.*

ABSTRACT

Natural food color is partially lost during food processing and storage, decreasing the product's appearance and commercial acceptability. To overcome this problem, industries add synthetic dyes to food formulations and one of the most used classes of synthetic dyes are the azo ones. Despite US-FDA having regulatory oversight for color additives, there are extensive data on the potential health risks or long-term cumulative toxicity of azo dyes [1-5]. Human serum albumin (HSA) is the main carrier of compounds in the bloodstream and some azo dyes used in beverages or in a variety of foodstuffs interact with HSA and can negatively impact the biodistribution of drugs and metabolites, e.g., citrus red 2 (E121), carmoisine (E122), and allura red AC (E129) [2-5]. Amaranth (E123) and new coccine (E124) are commercial food dyes that have not yet been evaluated in terms of biophysical profile in presence of HSA, thus, the present work reports this interaction by UV-visible, circular dichroism, steady-state, and time-resolved fluorescence combined with molecular docking and dynamics simulation. In the future we want to evaluate the impact of the presence of these dyes in the bloodstream on the pharmacokinetic profile of clinically approved drugs.

The interaction HSA:Dyes is spontaneous ($\Delta G^\circ < 0$) and moderate ($K_{SV} \approx 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$) being enthalpically ($\Delta H^\circ < 0$) and entropically ($\Delta S^\circ > 0$) driven, without significantly perturbing the secondary structure of HSA. There is one main binding site ($n \approx 1$) and subdomain IIA (site I), where Trp-214 residue can be found, is the main binding region for both studied dyes. Site I is the main binding region for widely clinically used anticoagulant and anti-inflammatory drugs, e.g., warfarin, phenylbutazone, dicoumarol, diflunisal, and naproxen [6,7], indicating that amaranth and new coccine might impact the pharmacokinetics of these medicines.

Acknowledgements: The Coimbra Chemistry Centre is supported by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT). O.A.C. thanks FCT for his PhD fellowship 2020.07504.BD.

References: [1] Al Reza, M.S.; et al. *Food Sci. Nutr.* 7 (2019) 667. [2] Wu, D.; et al. *Sci. Rep.* 9 (2019) 1615. [3] Wu, D.; et al. *Food. Chem.* 170 (2015) 423. [4] Basu, A.; Kumar, G.S. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 273 (2014) 200 [5] Wang, L.; et al. *Mol. Biol. Rep.* 41 (2014) 3381. [6] Sudlow, G.; et al. *Mol. Pharmacol.* 11 (1975) 824. [7] Sudlow, G. et al. 12 (1976) 1052.

P30. IMPLICATIONS OF AQUAPORIN-3 AND AQUAPORIN-5 ON PANCREATIC CANCER CELL BIOMECHANICS AND CELL-CELL ADHESION

Patrícia M. Silva^{1*}, **Inês V. da Silva**^{2,3}, **Maria J. Sarmiento**¹, **Ítala C. Silva**¹, **Filomena A. Carvalho**¹, **Graça Soveral**^{2,3}, and **Nuno C. Santos**¹

¹ Instituto de Medicina Molecular, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, 1649-028 Lisbon, Portugal;

² Research Institute for Medicines (iMed.Ulisboa), Faculty of Pharmacy, Universidade de Lisboa, 1649-003 Lisbon, Portugal;

³ Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Medicines, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universidade de Lisboa, 1649-003 Lisbon, Portugal

(**Email:* patriciamsilva@medicina.ulisboa.pt)

Keywords: aquaporins; pancreatic cancer; cell–cell adhesion; membrane fluidity; atomic force microscopy

ABSTRACT

Aquaporins are membrane channels responsible for the bidirectional transfer of water and small non-charged solutes across cell membranes. AQP3 and AQP5 are overexpressed in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma, playing key roles in cell migration, proliferation, and invasion. Here, we evaluated AQP3 and AQP5 involvement in cell biomechanical properties, cell–cell adhesion, and cell migration, following a loss-of-function strategy on BxPC-3 cells. Silencing of AQP3 and AQP5 was functionally validated by reduced membrane permeability and had implications on cell migration, slowing wound recovery. Moreover, silenced AQP5 and AQP3/5 cells showed higher membrane fluidity. Biomechanical and morphological changes were assessed by atomic force microscopy (AFM), revealing AQP5 and AQP3/5 silenced cells with a lower stiffness than their control. Through cell–cell adhesion measurements, the work (energy) necessary to detach two cells was found to be lower for AQP-silenced cells than control, showing that these AQPs have implications on cell–cell adhesion. These findings highlight AQP3 and AQP5 involvement in the biophysical properties of cell membranes, whole cell biomechanical properties, and cell–cell adhesion, thus having potential implication in the settings of tumor development.

P31. THE ROLE OF RuvBL1/2 IN THE ASSEMBLY OF PROTEIN-RNA snoRNP COMPLEXES

Philipp Busse^{1,2}, Ana C. F. Paiva^{1,2}, Pedro M. Matias^{1,2}, Tiago M. Bandeiras^{1,2}, Pedro M. F. Sousa^{1,2}

¹ iBET, Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica, Apartado 12, 2781-901 Oeiras, Portugal;

² Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Av. da República, 2780-157 Oeiras, Portugal

(*) *Email:* philipp.busse@ibet.pt

Keywords: *ATPases, RuvBLs, Cryo-EM, X-ray Crystallography, snoRNPs.*

ABSTRACT

RuvBL1 and RuvBL2 (R1R2) are highly conserved eukaryotic proteins of the AAA+ ATPase family, and closely related to the bacterial ATP-dependent DNA helicase RuvB. They form oligomeric rings, assemble into homo-hexamers, hetero-hexamers and/or hetero-dodecamers, and bear a regulatory Domain (DII) which is unique within the AAA+ ATPase superfamily. R1R2 are key players in transcription, mitosis, apoptosis, and other cellular events. They not only integrate different large molecular complexes such as Ino80 and R2TP, but also ensure the assembly of macromolecular complexes like snoRNPs, namely: the U4-U6-U5 spliceosome, the Box H/ACA snoRNP, the Box C/D snoRNP and the Telomerase complex, making them an attractive drug-target. The molecular mechanisms behind R1R2's role during snoRNP assembly processes are still unknown. Hence, the aim of this work is to shed light on their early assembly, starting with the translation of crucial protein components like the catalytic active DKC1 in Box H/ACA snoRNPs. After translation DKC1 might interact with SHQ1 which can act as a chaperone and prevent unspecific interaction of DKC1 with RNAs. Subsequently, SHQ1 may guide the complex to the nucleus where the complex is thought to interact with R1R2 to facilitate the maturation of Box H/ACA snoRNP complexes. To characterize and follow the formation of the different complexes we will use size exclusion chromatography, dynamic light scattering, differential scanning fluorimetry and, surface plasmon resonance. After the confirmation of stable complex formation, we aim to determine the 3D structures of these complexes using X-ray crystallography and Cryo-EM.

P32. TUMOR LIPID SIGNATURES DESCRIPTIVE OF ACQUISITION OF RESISTANCE TO ENDOCRINE THERAPY IN AN ENDOCRINE-RELATED BREAST CANCER MOUSE MODEL.

Rita Araújo¹, Caroline Lamb², Victoria Fabris², Claudia Lanari², Luisa Helguero³ and Ana M. Gil¹

¹ Department of Chemistry and CICECO - Aveiro Institute of Materials (CICECO/UA), University of Aveiro, Portugal

² Instituto de Biología y Medicina Experimental (IBYME), CONICET, Buenos Aires, Argentina

³ iBIMED—Institute for Biomedicine, Department of Medical Sciences, Universidade de Aveiro, Portugal

^(*) Email: anarita.asilva@ua.pt

Keywords: *Breast cancer, metabolomics, NMR, therapy resistente, mouse model*

ABSTRACT

Breast cancer (BC) is the most common type of cancer in women and, in most cases, it is hormone-dependent (HD), thus relying on estrogen and progesterone to activate intracellular receptors and stimulate tumor growth. Endocrine therapy (ET) is the primary treatment strategy, however, about half of the patients develop resistance in time. This involves progression to a hormone independent (HI) tumor, initially therapy-responsive and, subsequently resistant (HIR). The mechanisms that promote HI to HIR conversion are varied, and not completely understood.

With our work we aim to characterize the specific lipid signatures associated to the acquisition of hormonal independence and of ET-resistance, using NMR metabolomics. Tumor tissue and non-compromised mammary gland were analyzed, obtained from the medroxyprogesterone acetate (MPA)-induced BC mouse model. Compared to healthy tissue, tumors samples exhibited a continuous decrease of fatty acids (PUFA) associated signals along tumor progression stages, including linoleic acid. This result suggests a higher endurance to the peroxidation process in the more advanced stages (HI and HIR vs HD+MPA). Additionally, the significant decrease of saturated FA associated signals in tumors compared to mammary gland suggests a supporting role of FA oxidation in the malignant phenotype. Significant increases of different phospholipids suggest a phospholipid-directed metabolism in all tumor types. Finally, we noted increase of free cholesterol which has been reported as a common supporter of cell proliferation, invasion, and drug-resistance. In summary, our study on hormonal-independent and therapy-resistant breast cancer model identified significant changes in lipid metabolism, highlighting the importance of these metabolites in cancer.

P33. ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES AND IONIC LIQUIDS AS PARTNERS AGAINST BACTERIAL INFECTIONS

Ana Rita Ferreira^(*), Ana Gomes¹, Luísa Aguiar¹, Lucinda J. Bessa², Mariana Ferreira¹, Cátia Teixeira¹, Paula Gomes¹ and Paula Gameiro¹

¹ LAQV-REQUIMTE, Departamento de Química e Bioquímica, Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade do Porto, 4169-007 Porto, Portugal.

² Centro de Investigação Interdisciplinar Egas Moniz (CiIEM), Egas Moniz - Cooperativa de Ensino Superior, CRL, 2829-511 Almada, Portugal.

(*) Email: ritaferreira@fc.up.pt

Keywords: *Antibiotic resistance, Antimicrobial peptides, Ionic liquids, Large unilamellar vesicles, Fluorescence spectroscopy*

ABSTRACT

In the Era of antibiotic resistance, there is an urgent call for new antibiotic-like molecules that can work as a therapeutic strategy to fight multi-drug resistant (MDR) bacteria, such is the case of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) and ionic liquids (ILs). AMPs are typically cationic, amphipathic and display a membrane-targeting activity, with a fast-killing kinetics, being less prone to induce mechanisms of bacterial resistance. ILs are composed of organic cations and organic/inorganic anions with melting temperatures usually below 100 °C, which are being widely explored in the pharmaceutical field to improve drug solubility, to rescue old drugs, or as antimicrobial agents *per se*.

We propose an AMP-based strategy based on covalent and non-covalent conjugation of AMPs with alkyimidazolium bromide ILs, aiming at boosting the therapeutic potential of AMPs. Two cecropin-melittin-derived AMPs (BP100¹ and W-BP100², the later with an additional N-terminal Trp) were combined with imidazolium-based ILs containing a 12-carbon alkyl chain, reported to have antibacterial and antibiofilm properties³. The AMP-ILs were prepared through covalent conjugation using “click chemistry”⁴ or by non-covalent conjugation (equimolar mixtures). The antibacterial and haemolytic activities of AMP-IL conjugates were firstly screened and the interactions of the most promising compounds with large unilamellar vesicles (LUVs) of bacteria and eukaryotic cells were evaluated by steady-state fluorescence spectroscopy, circular dichroism, and dynamic light scattering.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by FCT/MCTES (UIDB/50006/2020 [UIDP/50006/2020]) and POCI through FEDER/COMPETE 2020 (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-031798) and through the project AMAZING (CIRCNA/BRB/0281/2019). ARF thanks M2B-PhD and FCT for a PhD fellowship (PD/BD137128/2018).

References: [1] Ferre et al. *Biophys J* 2009, 96(5), 1815. [2] Ferreira et al. *Membranes (Basel)* 2021, 11(1), 48. [3] Florio et al. *Mater Sci Eng C Mater Biol Appl* 2019, 104, 109907. [4] Gomes et al. *Int J Mol Sci* 2020, 21(17), 6174.

P34. THE IMPACT OF SARS-COV-2 OMICRON VARIANT ON THE HUMAN ACE2 BINDING: A COMPUTATIONAL STUDY

R. Teixeira^{1(*)}, M. Valério¹, L. Borges-Araújo¹, M. N. Melo¹, J. B. Vicente¹, D. Lousa¹, C. M. Soares¹

¹ Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Oeiras, Lisbon, Portugal

(*) *Email:* ri.teixeira@itqb.unl.pt

Keywords: *SARS-CoV-2, Receptor-binding domain, Variants of concern, Molecular dynamic simulation, Omicron*

ABSTRACT

Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is the causative agent of the COVID-19 pandemic, which escalated into a global pandemic in early 2020, accounting for >500 million infections and >6 million confirmed deaths worldwide. The SARS-CoV-2 mechanism of transmission and infection involves the binding of the virus to the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) host receptor through the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the spike (S) protein. The RBD is a privileged target of our immune system and antiviral therapies. Although multiple vaccines and new therapeutics against SARS-CoV-2 have been developed, their effectiveness is challenged by the emergence of new variants of concern (VOC) with reported mutations on the RBD. Those mutations are associated with higher transmissibility or the ability to escape the immune response of previously infected patients. [1] In late 2021, the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron VOC raised considerable global concern due to the presence of about 40 mutations in the S protein, 15 of which occur in the RBD. [2] Here we investigated the impact of the VOC RBD mutations on its interaction with ACE2, with a major focus on the Omicron RBD, by performing molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of this complex. Our analysis of the binding and structural dynamics of these mutations provided a detailed characterization of the binding mode between the VOC RBDs and the receptor. This allowed us to understand the role of key residues in the VOC RBD-ACE2 interface and the effect of specific substitutions on the binding affinity via the establishment of new interprotein contacts.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through the grant PTDC/CCI-BIO/28200/2017, by Project LISBOA-01-0145-FEDER-007660 (Microbiologia Molecular, Estrutural e Celular) funded by FEDER and FCT, and LS4FUTURE Associated Laboratory (LA/P/0087/2020).

References:

- [1] Greaney, A.J. et al. (2021) Cell Host Microbe 29,4457
- [2] Mannar D et al. (2022) Science 375,760764.

P35. THE ANALYSIS OF *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* NDH2 COARSEGRAIN SIMULATIONS MIGHT BE THE BEGINNING TO UNVEIL A FUTURE THERAPEUTICAL TARGET

R. Barriga^{1 (*)}, **M.M. Pereira**², **M.N. Melo**¹

¹ Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Lisbon, Portugal

² BioISI Biosystems & Integrative Sciences Institute, Faculty of Sciences of University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal

(*) *Email:* rodrigo.alves@itqb.unl.pt

Keywords: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *NDH-2*, *Coarse-Grain*, *Martini3*.

ABSTRACT

Some strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* have been gaining resistance to several antibiotics, raising the possibility of a future pandemic. Therefore, diminishing their virulence is of the utmost importance. Studies have shown a connection between Type II NADH: menaquinone oxidoreductase (NDH2) and *S. aureus* virulence. NDH2 has thus promising therapeutical potential, highlighting the importance of studies of its role in respiration in general and of its binding site mechanisms in particular. We've employed CoarseGrain (CG) simulations to represent *in silico* the substrate approximation that occurs in the binding site *in vivo*. All the compounds related to this study, such as FAD (NDH2 prosthetic group), NADH, menaquinone and derivatives, were all parameterised using the most recent Martini3 force-field parameters.

To perform the CG simulations, an *S. aureus* membrane of representative lipid composition was modelled together with NDH2.

Preliminary results show the preference of quinones for one of the NDH2 binding sites (there's a separate site for NADH that the quinones don't visit). In addition, the reduction of quinones to quinols lowers their affinity for the binding site, thus promoting product egress. This hints that the binding site environment may be specifically tuned to discriminate the quinone from the quinol as a means to increase turnover.

Our results show that CG Molecular Dynamics is well suited to studying NDH2 substrate/product dynamics and could possibly be extended to other *S. aureus* oxidoreductases. Ultimately, we hope that with these approaches, we'll be able to identify new and vital targets in the fight against bacterial resistance.

Acknowledgements: FCT (FUNDAÇÃO PARA A CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA), ITQB (MOSTMICRO).

P36. NON-STRUCTURAL PROTEIN 1 (NS1) AS A DRUG TARGET FOR SEASONAL AND PANDEMIC INFLUENZA

Rui João Loureiro^{1(*)}, **Andreia Cunha**¹, **Nícia Rosário-Ferreira**¹, **Rui M. M. Brito**¹

¹ Coimbra Chemistry Center - Institute of Molecular Sciences (CQC-IMS), Chemistry Department, Faculty of Sciences and Technology,

University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

(*) *Email:* rloureiro@qui.uc.pt

Keywords: *Influenza, NS1, Molecular Dynamics, Druggability, Protein-Protein Interactions.*

ABSTRACT

Influenza viruses are responsible for significant morbidity and mortality worldwide in winter seasonal outbreaks and in flu pandemics. Influenza viruses have a high rate of evolution, severely diminishing the effectiveness of the available antivirals and making the development of new ones that could target different virus variants an urgent need. One of the most promising new targets for influenza antiviral therapy is the non-structural protein 1 (NS1), a highly conserved protein exclusively expressed in virus-infected cells that mediates essential functions in virus replication and pathogenesis. We therefore explored the druggability of NS1 from different strains of influenza using molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and druggability predictions.

Druggability predictions over 100 ns MD simulations suggest potential druggable sites in NS1 that are common to several influenza strains. Moreover, some of these sites co-localize with the binding interfaces of NS1 with several host proteins such as CPSF30, PI3K and TRIM25.

The data presented provide rationale for targeting NS1 in new large-spectrum influenza antiviral development aimed at effectively tackling both seasonal outbreaks and future pandemics.

Acknowledgements:

This work was funded by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, I.P. (FCT), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), and COMPETE 2020 through grant PTDC/QUI-OUT/32572/2017 “Leads4FLU - Novel antivirals against Influenza: NS1 target validation and lead discovery” and by FCT through the project with the references UIDB/00313/2020 and UIDP/0013/2020. Rui João Loureiro acknowledges support from University of Coimbra through contract IT057-20-9919 and computational resources from FCCN LCA-UC Navigator. Andreia Cunha and Nícia Rosário-Ferreira acknowledge support from FCT through doctoral fellowships PD/BD/143131/2018 and PD/BD/135179/2017, respectively.

P37. UNFOLDING EXTRACELLULAR ELECTRON TRANSFER MECHANISMS WITH ALPHAFOLD

Tomás M. Fernandes^{1,2(*)}, Jorge M. A. Antunes^{1,2}, Leonor Morgado^{1,2}, Carlos A. Salgueiro^{1,2}

¹ Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, Caparica, Portugal

² UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Caparica, Portugal

(*) *Email:* tmo.fernandes@campus.fct.unl.pt

Keywords: *Geobacter, Extracellular electron transfer, Multiheme cytochromes, AlphaFold.*

ABSTRACT

AlphaFold has recently delivered a revolutionary advance for protein structure prediction by using a novel machine learning approach that incorporates both genetic and structural database searches [1]. AlphaFold predicts protein structures to near experimental accuracy and the incorporation of this tool within structural biology will greatly accelerate the advancement of the field. In this work, we showcase how AlphaFold can be used to obtain crucial information about electron transfer proteins, specifically multiheme cytochromes, the known key players of extracellular electron transfer (EET) in electroactive bacteria [2]. Previous structure prediction methods typically failed to deliver reliable protein models, especially in the definition of the heme pocket, which can be confidently predicted using AlphaFold by mapping the typical residues involved in the heme coordination. The calculated structures of the components of the EET networks of the electroactive *Geobacter sulfurreducens* bacterium, here used as model, revealed information about heme axial coordination, heme spatial disposition, overall fold arrangement, as well as insights on the assembly of multiprotein complexes. Based on the obtained models, an overview of the EET networks of *G. sulfurreducens* will be presented. Interestingly, in addition to the predictions of the electron transfer properties of multiheme cytochromes *in silico*, the data obtained can be further explored to accelerate the production of these proteins for *in vitro* studies, by providing important information for cloning, expression and purification strategies. Overall, we can state that AlphaFold will be a particularly resourceful tool towards the general understanding of EET mechanisms in bacteria.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through the following grants: SFRH/BD/145039/2019 (TMF), SFRH/BPD/114848/2016 (LM), PTDC/BIA-BQM-31981/2017 (CAS), PTDC/BIA-BQM/4967/2020 (CAS) and EXPL/BIA-BQM/0770/2021 (LM). This work was also supported by national funds from FCT within projects UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 (UCIBIO) and project LA/P/0140/2020 (i4HB).

References:

[1] John Jumper et al., *Nature*, 596, 583-589, 2021.

[2] Thomas A. Clarke, *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.*, 66, 56-62, 2022.

P38. TOWARDS THE DESIGN OF DRUG-LIKE COMPOUNDS THAT BREAK AMYLOID FIBRILS: TRANSTHYRETIN, A CASE-STUDY

Zaida L. Almeida^{1(*)}, Elisabete Ferreira¹, Pedro F. Cruz¹, Carlos J. V. Simões^{1,2}, Rui M. M. Brito¹

¹ Chemistry Department and Coimbra Chemistry Centre-Institute of Molecular Sciences (CQC-IMS), University of Coimbra, 3004-535 Coimbra, Portugal

² BSIM Therapeutics, Coimbra, Portugal

(*) *Email:* zalmeida@qui.uc.pt

Keywords: *amyloid fibrils, amyloidosis, QSAR study, FIBREAKERS, disaggregation assays.*

ABSTRACT

In degenerative, debilitating, and incurable pathological conditions such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, soluble proteins undergo conformational changes and aggregate into insoluble intra- or extracellular amyloid fibrils. Many structural features are shared by amyloid fibrils from different precursor proteins, namely long and unbranched filaments with cross- β sheet conformation. To date, more than 40 proteins have been associated to more than 50 diseases characterized by protein amyloid deposits, known as amyloidoses.¹ A possible therapeutic strategy to overcome amyloid deposition is amyloid fibril disaggregation. In recent years, this approach was translated into several clinical trials (CT) conducted for different amyloidoses. However, most of these CT failed, despite the significant advances in the understanding of amyloid diseases. The conventional process of drug discovery is extremely challenging, time-consuming, and expensive. Today, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Cheminformatics and Bioinformatics tools are helping in this process and potentially reduce the time, cost and attrition rate of drug development. In this study, in a first phase, we used a battery of *in silico* methods to understand the physicochemical and structural rules that govern the ability of certain compounds to interact and disaggregate preformed amyloid fibrils into soluble aggregates. Firstly, we carried out an extensive literature search to identify compounds with activity in amyloid fibril disruption, either *in vitro* or *in vivo*. A selection of 606 compounds, here named FIBREAKERS, formed a structurally diverse chemical library with activity against 29 different amyloid precursor proteins. This FIBREAKER library was analyzed according to several physicochemical properties, and compounds were also classified according to their drug-like and toxicity profile, and clustered based on structural similarities. Currently, quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models are under development. In a second phase, a specific *in vitro* screening protocol here developed will be used to further test the activity of the FIBREAKERS selected from the QSAR models. Transthyretin (TTR), a protein known to aggregate into amyloid fibrils and cause several diseases,¹ was selected as a case study. Five aggregation protocols using different experimental conditions were studied by DLS and TEM, in the presence and absence of one of the most studied FIBREAKERS – doxycycline – as a positive control. STD NMR experiments were also performed to study the interaction of doxycycline with preformed TTR fibrils. Results show that each aggregation protocol produces amyloid species with different morphologies, which can be an advantage to mimic *in vivo* conditions, when testing FIBREAKERS in amyloid disruption assays.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through grant UID/QUI/00313/2019, and programs COMPETE and CENTRO-2020. Z.L.A also thanks FCT for doctoral fellowship SFRH/BD/137991/2018.

P39. FUNCTIONALISATION OF HFCVD DIAMOND FOR THE RECOGNITION OF BIOMOLECULES

Nádia E. Santos^{1,2}, Flávio Figueira³, Miguel Neto³, Samuel Guieu^{1,3}, Jonas Deuermeier⁴, Filipe A. Almeida Paz³, Joana C. Mendes², Susana S. Braga¹

¹ LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, 3810-193, Aveiro, Portugal

² Instituto de Telecomunicações e Departamento de Eletrónica, Telecomunicações e Informática, Universidade de Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal;

³ CICECO—Aveiro Institute of Materials, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal;

⁴ GENIMAT|3N, Department of Materials Science, School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon and CEMOP/UNINOVA, 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal

(*) *Email:* nadiaasantos@ua.pt

Keywords: *Hot-filament chemical deposition (HFCVD) diamond, photochemical grafting*

ABSTRACT

As-grown hot-filament chemical vapor deposition (HFCVD) diamond can be easily functionalised by photochemical methods, either with a UV lamp or laser light sources, which dramatically reduces the reaction time. Adequate functional groups are carboxylic acids or amine groups that permit the subsequent binding of enzymes, DNA or proteins. In the present work, we use boron-doped HFCVD diamond films as the substrate to demonstrate our functionalisation approach. The H-terminated surface was used to react with spacer ligands via photochemical reactions. This step was essential to create distance between the diamond surface and the functional group, to allow subsequent introduction on the surface of a wide variety of recognition units. The samples were tested for the contact angle, which showed expected alterations in the hydrophobicity of the surfaces. We expect to use this procedure to introduce recognition units to produce highly specific sensors for infectious diseases.

Acknowledgements:

This work is funded by National Funds through the FCT project UIDB/50025/2020-2023. Thanks are due to University of Aveiro, FCT/MCTES, PIDDAC, FEDER, PT2020 for financial support to LAQV-REQUIMTE (Ref. UIDB/50006/2020), CICECO—Aveiro Institute of Materials (Refs. UIDB/50011/2020, UIDP/50011/2020 & LA/P/0006/2020), Instituto de Telecomunicações (Refs UID/EEA/50008/2019 and UIDB/50008/2020-UIDP/50008/2020), and I3N LA/P/0037/2020, UIDP/50025/2020 and UIDB/50025/2020.

References:

N. E. Santos, F. Figueira, M. Neto, F. A. Almeida Paz, S.S. Braga, J. C. Mendes, *Appl. Sci.* 2022, 12, 3000; <https://doi.org/10.3390/app120630000>

2nd Meeting of Young Biophysicists

Biophysics *Festival 2022*

June 3rd | Aveiro

